
DELIVERABLE 3.4

GEP's Refinement and Next Steps

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Glossary

ATHENA SWAN - It is an equality charter mark framework and accreditation scheme for higher education and research institutions

COLOUR - COLlaborative innOvative sUustainable Regional univerSities

DEI – Diversity, Equity and Inclusion

GEAM - Gender Equality Audit and Monitoring

GEP – Gender Equality Plan

NGO - Non-Governmental Organization

EDI – Equality, Diversity & Inclusion

GBV – Gender Based Violence

D&I – Diversity and Inclusion

Introduction

This deliverable “*GEP’s Refinement and Next Steps*” is part of Work Package 3 – *Pilot Actions Implementation, Evaluation and GEP Refinement* of the NEXUS Project. It corresponds specifically to Task 3.3 – *Innovative GEPs towards sustainability*, coordinated by the Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (Italy). This document is based on the GEP’s Refinement Analysis made by partners (see Annex Section).

Its objective is twofold: first, to support and document the **refinement process of institutional Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)** conducted by NEXUS implementing partners; second, to identify and present **further inclusive** and innovative actions to be implemented beyond the project’s lifetime. This dual approach ensures that the project’s results are not only consolidated but also projected forward into future strategic planning.

The refinement process reflects a deep institutional reflection on the sustainability, replicability, and adaptability of NEXUS pilot actions, conducted through structured workshops and participatory analysis sessions held in each implementing institution. The outputs of these sessions serve as a basis for revising current GEPs and designing concrete next steps to foster long-term change and inclusive transformation in research-performing organizations.

1. NEXUS: project description, aims and objectives

The NEXUS project aims to bridge inclusive gaps in 9 research organizations and their respective ecosystems by designing, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating 45 targeted actions. These efforts focus on fostering institutional change through inclusive Gender Equality Plans (GEPs), leveraging both intersectional and intersectoral approaches. Intersectionality addresses overlapping inequalities such as race, gender, age, and socio-economic status, while emphasizing partnerships across sectors, including universities, NGOs, and private organizations, to enhance impact.

The project employs 9 context-sensitive strategies for action piloting in various regions across Member States and Associating Countries, promoting geographical inclusiveness. By establishing structures in less experienced institutions, NEXUS enables them to exceed Horizon Europe's minimum GEP requirements through a participatory, multi-stakeholder process supported by a Twinning scheme of three "Twin Trios." Tailored capacity-building and training programs ensure comprehensive support.

Considering this, D3.4 centers on the third phase of the project, specifically activities within Work Package (WP) 3, which encompass pilot action implementation, evaluation, and GEP refinement through monitoring and redesign processes. Developing inclusive GEPs is an essential part of this European project. In light of the analyses, implementations, and adjustments carried out, the deliverable focuses on the main lessons learnt with a view to developing new GEP actions which are future-oriented and potentially applicable to an organization.

Particularly, D3.4 focuses on:

- a) The sustainability of the NEXUS pilot actions and if they are useful for GEPs' Refinement
- b) The design of further and innovative actions that each partner will implement after the end of the project

1.1 Purpose and scope of the T3.3 “Innovative GEP’s towards Sustainability”

This deliverable is part of **WP3 - Pilot Actions, Implementation, Evaluation, and GEP Refinement**. More precisely, T3.3 -**Innovative GEPs towards sustainability**. The task leader is the Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, with Lina Donnarumma, Vanessa De Luca and Martina Cicaloni as primary contacts.

The Task D3.3 Pilot Action Results fall under the **T3.2 – Monitoring, Evaluation and Ongoing Redesign**. **Within that task**, It builds on the lessons learnt through the actions' implementation phase and the evaluation activities reported in D3.3. While D3.3 synthesizes the results of the pilot actions, in D3.4 partners worked in synergy to:

a) assess the NEXUS Actions in terms of sustainability: starting from the results of the formative and summative evaluation, each NEXUS partner focused on assessing the sustainability of the NEXUS actions implemented in their institution. As part of this phase of the NEXUS project, this internal analysis aimed to assess the sustainability of the inclusive actions co-designed and implemented within each institution's Gender Equality Plan (GEP). This reflection served to identify which actions are likely to be replicable, scalable, and resilient in the face of institutional change, while also retaining their intersectional and intersectoral integrity.

b) indicate the sustainable NEXUS Actions useful to be proposed for the refinement of their future GEPs: based on the sustainability analysis, each NEXUS implementing partner indicated the NEXUS actions (considering the modifications made during the formative and summative evaluation and the modifications required for the sustainability) that could be proposed for the next GEP .

c) identify/design one further inclusive action: each partner designed a further innovative and inclusive action to be implemented after the end of the NEXUS Project. The design of this action was done following the methodology and tools included in D2.2 "*Methodology for pilot actions design*". This activity is part of the "Dissemination and communication report and sustainability plan" included in the work package 5 Impact. This document required each partner to submit a sustainability report containing at least one innovative and inclusive action to be piloted after the end of the project (one action per Partner).

The GEP refinement process aims to improve and enhance Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The process includes carrying out a **GEP refinement analysis session** to promote inclusivity and gender equality within research and innovation institutions.

The GEP Refinement process entailed:

- **Methodology:** based on the lessons learned from the NEXUS project, a methodology was developed to guide the design of future GEP iterations. **Analysis:** building on formative evaluations results and redesign processes, each partner assessed the sustainability of NEXUS Actions. This evaluation considered multiple dimensions including costs, personnel

involved, adaptability to changes, replicability, structural integrity, flexibility, extensibility, and impact on inclusiveness.

- **Identification:** after conducting the analysis, each partner identified which pilot actions could be proposed to their Institution for the next iteration of GEP.

1.2 Relation to other tasks and work packages

Alignment with WP3 objectives

WP3 is dedicated to implementing the actions co-created in WP2, monitoring their progress, and evaluating their outcomes. WP3's main objective is the implementation of the actions identified in WP2. Each partner implemented at least 5 inclusive actions. WP3 also dealt with the monitoring and evaluation process - both formative and summative- integrated into an ongoing redesign process. D3.4 "*GEP's refinement and next steps*" is built on the experiences that the partners gained during the year of implementation of the NEXUS actions, and on the evaluation and analysis conducted and presented in D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3. The final analysis presented in D3.4 outlines a comprehensive vision of each organization's GEP and provides detail of which areas of their GEP have improved or changed and how, as well as what would be feasible or sustainable to implement and develop in future GEPs. Finally, part of this GEP refinement work has involved partners in drafting the design of potential new future action.

Connections to previous deliverables (D3.1, D3.2, D3.3)

D3.4 "*GEP's Refinement and Next Steps*" is the final output of WP3 and is built upon the methodological and evaluative trajectory established through D3.1, D3.2. and D3.3. Specifically, D3.1 laid the foundation by defining the monitoring and evaluation framework for piloted actions, while D3.2 reported the formative evaluation results from the first phase of implementation. D3.3 provides a comprehensive account of both the first and second rounds of evaluation — formative and summative — thus offering essential evidence that informed the refinement process of institutional GEPs described in this report. D3.4 consolidates these findings and completes the WP3 cycle by translating lessons learned into sustainable action plans and strategic revisions of GEPs across partner institutions.

Connection with WP5- Impact

D3.4 aligns closely with the objectives of WP5 particularly in terms of impact, dissemination, and long-term sustainability. The refinement of GEPs and the identification of sustainable and replicable actions feeds into D5.4 – Dissemination and Communication Report and Sustainability Plan – by highlighting the institutional commitments, mechanisms, and actions that are likely to be maintained and developed after the end of the project. This alignment ensures that the sustainability dimension of WP3 is fully integrated into the broader dissemination, exploitation, and impact strategy of WP5.

The refined GEP actions identified through the NEXUS implementation and evaluation cycles represent not only institutional progress but also valuable knowledge of assets with potential for wider uptake. The further actions proposed by partner institutions, which range from inclusive mentoring schemes to communication guidelines and new gender-sensitive governance tools, constitute a key input for external communication and policy dialogue under WP5. Moreover, the sustainability dimension of the refined GEPs, as documented in this deliverable, directly informs the sustainability mechanisms to be outlined in D5.4 “Dissemination and Communication Report and Sustainability Plan”. Insights from the refinement process—particularly those related to structural embedding, cultural transformation, and adaptive planning—will feed into the Exploitation Plan, ensuring that NEXUS results continue to produce impact beyond the project’s lifespan.

2. Methodological background

2.1 Structure of the refinement methodology

The GEP refinement methodology was designed by Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, to ensure a structured, participatory, and sustainability-oriented approach across all NEXUS implementing partners. Rooted in the evidence collected through the formative and summative evaluations, the process guided each partner in assessing the long-term viability of their pilot actions and in planning further steps.

The methodology consisted of the following key elements:

- **Refinement Analysis Sessions:** Each partner organized a dedicated analysis session by the end of May 2025, involving GEP working groups and NEXUS team members. These sessions were structured to include reflection on implementation results, assessment of sustainability across five dimensions (organizational, operational, cultural, strategic, and adaptive), and the co-design of one additional inclusive and innovative action to be implemented after the project.
- **Standardized Templates and Reporting Tools:** To ensure comparability and coherence across partners, the refinement process made use of standard reporting templates (Annex A, B, and C), covering summaries of sessions, sustainability analysis, and future action design. Partners were asked to upload their completed templates to the central SharePoint repository by mid-June 2025.
- **Evaluation Criteria:** Sustainability was assessed using a multidimensional framework, considering not only the continuity of actions, but also their capacity to be embedded, adapted, scaled, replicable, resilient in the face of institutional change, supported within the institutional ecosystem and retaining their intersectional and intersectoral integrity. To facilitate the discussion, the methodology required partners to fill in a table (table 1 in Annex C) for each pilot action to report the results of their discussion in terms of sustainability. The methodology equips project partners with a structured set of questions designed to evaluate the sustainability of each pilot initiative. This assessment framework considers five key dimensions: organizational, operational, cultural, strategic, and adaptive. By applying this

approach, the methodology ensured a consistent and comparable evaluation across all 45 pilot actions implemented within the NEXUS project. The methodology provides also a description of each sustainability dimension.

- **Guiding Questions:** the guided questions developed for each sustainability dimension were as follows:

Organizational sustainability: *is the action embedded in your institution's structures, policies, or routines? Is it supported by institutional roles, resources, or formal commitments?*

Adaptive sustainability: *how is adaptability to changes of action? Can it be adjusted to accommodate evolving internal and external circumstances? Is the action adaptable to future changes (e.g., leadership, funding, priorities)? What would help it stay resilient?*

Operational sustainability: *how is the replicability/flexibility of the action? How can the action be duplicated in different contexts, without significant additional costs? Can the action be scaled up or replicated in other departments, other segments of the populations or other institutions? What factors would support or limit this?*

Strategic sustainability: *how is the structural integrity of the action? Can the actions be maintained over time? How are the risks of the action? What are the biggest risks to the continuation of this action? How might these risks be mitigated?*

Cultural sustainability: *How is the extensibility of the action? Can the action include more dimensions, thereby enhancing intersectionality? What impact has the action had so far—on people, practices, or policies—and how do you see this evolving?*

- **Timeline and Coordination:** The process followed a coordinated timeline aligned with the end of the implementation phase and summative evaluation

2.2 Design of one new innovative and inclusive action

Partners were encouraged to identify or develop ideas informed by the methodologies from Work Package 2, while also critically assessing gaps in their current Gender Equality Plans. (Annex C Table C3).

2.3 Tool used (analysis sessions, templates, evaluations)

At the end of the analysis session, each partner completed:

- **the Analysis Session Summary Template (Annex A)**
- **the Sustainability Report (Annex C Nr. 2)**
- **the table C.3) provided in Annex C** related to the further action approved and designed

To ensure that the process was carried out properly, the Italian Institute of Technology (IIT) prepared an Excel file in which partners were asked to enter the scheduled date for their analysis session.

2.4 Timeline and participants

Each partner uploaded the completed Annex A and C (Table nr.2 and Table C.3) to the folders reserved for each institution located in the WP3 “Pilot Actions Implementation, Evaluation and GEP Refinement” of TUD SharePoint no later than **June 15, 2025**.

2.5 Coordination and support provided to partners

Central support was provided by IIT to assist partners in designing, conducting, and documenting the refinement of activities, through the sharing of the methodology and of a document explaining the single steps. During a Board Meeting held in April, IIT explained the methodology and procedures to partners. After that, the document Methodology for GEP’s Refinement was uploaded on the TUD SharePoint together with all related templates. IIT scheduled an individual meeting with partners that requested clarification.

The results of this comprehensive process are synthesized in this deliverable (Chapters 3-6), offering a shared foundation for institutional change and sustainability planning across the NEXUS partnership.

2.6 Summary of the Sessions Conducted

As part of the NEXUS project’s final phase, each partner institution organized dedicated GEP refinement sessions between **April and July 2025**. These workshops were designed to revisit and

evaluate the gender equality actions piloted during the implementation phase, assess their sustainability, and identify new inclusive practices to be integrated into future Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).

All participating institutions (Technological University of Dublin, Frederick University, Sofia University, University of Le Mans, AGH University, Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research, University of Nis, Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia and Koç University) held participatory workshops or structured meetings involving internal stakeholders such as HR representatives, researchers, students, EDI officers, leadership, and administrative staff. The main goals of these sessions were to reflect on lessons learned, critically assess pilot actions, and define the post-project roadmap. Technological University of Dublin, for organizational issues, organized single interviews with people involved in the analysis.

3. Sustainability Analysis of NEXUS Actions

The refinement sessions conducted across NEXUS partner institutions provided a structured opportunity to critically review the initial Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and assess the sustainability of the pilot actions, identifying those that had demonstrated significant potential for integration into existing structures, those which required further adaptation, and those which would be incorporated into future iterations of the GEP. Building on the methodology defined in D 2.2 and the monitoring framework set out in D3.1 and D3.2, partners were able to reflect on lessons learned from both formative and summative evaluation cycles.

The results show a strong alignment between institutional needs, data collection processes and areas covered by the GEP framework, namely:

- Work-life balance and organizational culture
- Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
- Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
- Gender dimension in research and teaching content
- Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

Importantly, some actions were confirmed as structurally embedded within partner institutions, while others are to be included in the next GEP cycles. This dual outcome illustrates both the short-term achievements of NEXUS pilot actions and their potential for long-term sustainability.

3.1 Sustainability assessment criteria (organizational, operational, cultural, strategic, adaptive)

3.1.1 Technological University of Dublin (TU Dublin)

Table 1

Partners	Actions involved in Gep's Refinement Analysis	GEP's Area for actions involved/Data Collection Process	Trio Actions (Y/N)	Sustainability (Structural in the institution/to be Included in the new GEP)	Current GEP
Technological University Dublin (Ireland)	Bystander Intervention Training and Awareness Online Module	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	Y	Structural in the Institution	2022-2025
	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression- a Needs Analysis	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Y	Structural in the Institution	
	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Y	Structural in the Institution	
	EDI Info-Hub	Work Life Balance & Organizational Culture	N	Structural in the Institution	
	EDI Champions Network	Work Life Balance & Organizational Culture	N	Structural in the Institution	

3.1.2 Frederick University (FredU)

Table 2

Partners	Actions involved in Gep's Refinement Analysis	GEP's Area for actions involved/Data Collection Process	Trio Actions (Y/N)	Sustainability (Structural in the institution/to be Included in the new GEP)	Current GEP
Frederick University (Cyprus)	Annual training from an external speaker on Gender Equality and Intersectionality under the Personal and Professional Committee (P2DF)”	Work Life Balance & Organizational Culture	N	To be Included in the new GEP	2021-2025

3.1.3 Sofia University (UNISOFIA)

Table 3

Partners	Actions involved in Gep's Refinement Analysis	GEP's Area for actions involved/Data Collection Process	Trio Actions (Y/N)	Sustainability (Structural in the institution/to be Included in the new GEP)	Current GEP
Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski (Bulgary)	Data collection and percentage monitoring among students, PhDs, academic and administrative staff in Sofia University (related to gender, age, socioeconomic status,)	Data Collection Processes	N	Structural in the Institution	2021-2027
	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Y	Structural in the Institution	

3.1.4 Le Mans University (UM)

Table 4

Partners	Actions involved in Gep's Refinement Analysis	GEP's Area for actions involved/Data Collection Process	Trio Actions (Y/N)	Sustainability (Structural in the institution/to be Included in the new GEP)	Current GEP
Le Mans University (France)	Influence of biases in decision-making	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	2021-2023
	Gender & Intersectional Dimensions in Research	Gender dimension in research and teaching content	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	
	Parenting Resource Group	Work Life Balance & Organizational Culture	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	
	Fostering empowerment for women at work	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	N	To be Included in the new GEP	
	Gender, health and well-being	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	N	To be Included in the new GEP	

3.1.5 AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH)

Table 5

Partners	Actions involved in Gep's Refinement Analysis	GEP's Area for actions involved/Data Collection Process	Trio Actions (Y/N)	Sustainability (Structural in the institution/to be Included in the new GEP)	Current GEP
AGH University of Krakow (Poland)	Action E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality	Gender dimension in research and teaching content	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	2025-2028
	Inclusive communication guidelines	Work Life Balance & Organizational Culture	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	
	Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring (GEAM) Tool	Data Collection Processes	Y	Structural in the Institution	
	Fostering participation in work-related training through data collection with a gender+ perspective	Data Collection Processes	Y	Structural in the Institution	
	Information campaign	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	N	To be Included in the new GEP	

3.1.6 Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (BZN)

Table 6

Partners	Actions involved in Gep's Refinement Analysis	GEP's Area for actions involved/Data Collection Process	Trio Actions (Y/N)	Sustainability (Structural in the institution/to be Included in the new GEP)	Current GEP
Bay Zoltan Nonprofit Ltd for Applied Research (Hungary)	Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring (GEAM) Tool	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	2024_2026
	Inclusive communication guidelines	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	

3.1.7 University of Nis (UN)

Table 7

Partners	Actions involved in Gep's Refinement Analysis	GEP's Area for actions involved/Data Collection Process	Trio Actions (Y/N)	Sustainability (Structural in the institution/to be Included in the new GEP)	Current GEP
University of Nis (Serbia)	Influence of biases in decision-making	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	2021-2025
	Parenting Resource Group	Work Life Balance & Organizational Culture	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	
	Gender & Intersectional Dimensions in Research	Gender dimension in research and teaching content	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	
	Informing employees and students about the existence of the Regulation on Prevention and Protection from Sexual Harassment at FMEUNI (RonPPfromSH)	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	N	To be Included in the new GEP	
	Better environment for Roma students at the faculty	Work Life Balance & Organizational Culture	N	To be Included in the new GEP	

3.1.8 Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT)

Table 8

Partners	Actions involved in Gep's Refinement Analysis	GEP's Area for actions involved/Data Collection Process	Trio Actions (Y/N)	Sustainability (Structural in the institution/to be Included in the new GEP)	Current GEP
Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT)	Influence of the bias in decision making	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	2023-2025
	Recognizing and addressing Harassment in the workplace	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	N	To be Included in the new GEP	
	Gender and intersectional dimension in research	Gender dimension in research and teaching content	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	

3.1.9 Koç University (KU)

Table 9

Partners	Actions involved in Gep's Refinement Analysis	GEP's Area for actions involved/Data Collection Process	Trio Actions (Y/N)	Sustainability (Structural in the institution/to be Included in the new GEP)	Current GEP
Koç University (Turkey)	Bystander Intervention Training and Awareness Online Module	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	2022-2025
	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression- a Needs Analysis	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	
	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Y	To be Included in the new GEP	
	Skills Development Program (KU)	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	N	To be Included in the new GEP	

4. Overview of the Refinement Process

4.1 Reflections and lessons learned

The refinement of GEPs across the NEXUS consortium offered an opportunity not only to consolidate pilot actions but also to reflect on the conditions that enable or hinder sustainable gender equality interventions. Among the most salient **lessons learned**, partners recognized that actions are more likely to be sustained when they are **co-designed with stakeholders, aligned with existing institutional strategies**, and **supported by leadership and governance structures**. Embedding actions into routine processes such as recruitment, onboarding, performance appraisal, or research funding proved essential for ensuring their longevity beyond the project lifecycle.

Moreover, the refinement process highlighted the importance of **adaptive and iterative approaches**, allowing institutions to revise and reframe actions based on feedback and changing contexts. Actions that prioritized intersectionality, digital accessibility, and cross-departmental collaboration were particularly effective in building organizational trust and commitment.

However, several **common barriers** also emerged. Many institutions reported **limited human and financial resources**, especially for coordination and training. **Resistance to change**, particularly in STEM or hierarchical environments, remained a persistent obstacle. Other challenges included the **lack of centralized equality structures**, difficulties in engaging male staff or senior leadership, and **low institutional awareness** of how gender equality and intersectionality issues intersect with broader strategic goals (e.g., digital transformation, research excellence, student success).

Despite these barriers, institutions that adopted **flexible implementation methods**, invested in **capacity-building**, and fostered **communities of practice** were able to overcome initial inertia and make significant progress toward embedding gender equality as a shared, institutional responsibility.

4.2 Examples of good practices

The GEP refinement phase across NEXUS partner institutions surfaced several innovative, impactful, and context-sensitive actions that stand out as good practices due to their strong sustainability, transferability, and alignment with institutional strategies and Horizon Europe standards. These

practices were successful not only in implementation but also in securing long-term institutional embedding and potential for scale-up.

Inclusive Mentoring Program – Trio Action: The Twin Trio (TUD, KU, UNISOFIA) developed an evidence-based, scalable mentoring initiative built on prior needs assessment surveys. It addresses career progression, inclusive leadership, and work-life challenges. The program is modular, and supports different mentoring formats (e.g., peer, reverse).

Why does it stand out: Participatory design, cross-functional support, integration into strategic HR planning, strong adaptive and organizational sustainability.

E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality - Trio Action: The Twin Trio (AGH, FredU, BZN) created a modular e-course on gender and intersectionality, tailored to the university’s STEM-heavy profile.

Why does it stand out: Strong digital innovation; co-created with students and tech partners; culturally sensitive; scalable with low operational cost.

Integration of Gender and Inclusiveness into Research Support – Trio Action: The Twin Trio (IIT, UN, UM) developed guidelines and awareness-raising tools to embed gender and diversity considerations into research proposals. These were institutionalized through the Project Office and supported by leadership, enhancing both national compliance and EU funding readiness.

Why does it stand out: Strategic alignment with Horizon Europe; high relevance for researchers; integrated into existing research support systems.

These best practices exemplify the transformative potential of tailored gender equality interventions when supported by strong institutional buy-in, stakeholder engagement, and sustainability planning. They provide a solid foundation for future scaling within and beyond the NEXUS consortium.

4.3 Contributions to the future revision of GEPs

The refinement process contributed substantially to the future orientation of institutional GEPs. It enabled partners to:

- Consolidate pilot actions that demonstrated clear impact and feasibility (e.g., GBV training, inclusive mentoring, bias-aware recruitment)
- Identify scaling opportunities and cross-unit collaborations
- Integrate new intersectional dimensions (e.g., parenthood, ethnicity, digital accessibility)
- Embed adaptive mechanisms for regular feedback and revision (e.g., reflexive GEPs, living action plans)

Most importantly, the process empowered institutions to move beyond compliance and toward transformative, context-sensitive equality strategies. The alignment of these refined actions with national frameworks, EU policies, and Horizon Europe expectations ensures that GEPs will remain in dynamic instruments capable of responding to future challenges in research and higher education.

4.4 GEP's Refinement Composition and Future GEP Structure

Actions Proposed for GEP Refinement

The refinement process carried out by the NEXUS partner institutions led to the consolidation of 32 sustainable pilot actions out of the 45 initially developed, representing 71% of all pilot initiatives. These actions were selected for inclusion in revised versions of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) based on their demonstrated sustainability, institutional alignment, and stakeholder validation. Importantly, only those actions that were deemed structurally embedded or ready for policy inclusion were considered. The refinement process conducted by each NEXUS partner identified a core set of sustainable and high-impact actions that should be included in the next cycle of institutional Gender Equality Plans. These actions reflect both institutional learning and a strong alignment with the Horizon Europe framework. They are grouped below according to the GEP thematic areas defined by the European Commission:

Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Progression:

Actions promoting transparent selection criteria, fair evaluation of candidates, inclusive job advertisements, and mentoring programs for underrepresented groups.

Work-Life Balance and Organizational Culture: Measures supporting parenting policies, flexible working arrangements, and inclusive workplace cultures.

Gender Balance in Leadership and Decision-Making: Practices such as inclusive appointment procedures and the creation of gender-sensitive decision-making bodies.

Gender Dimension in Research and Teaching Content: Guidelines and training programs aimed at integrating intersectionality perspectives into research design and curricula.

Measures against Gender-Based Violence (GBV) including Sexual Harassment: Protocols for reporting and prevention, awareness campaigns, and survivor-centered institutional policies.

The **Data Collection and Monitoring processes** are not included among the 5 GEP areas proposed by Horizon Europe. They are standardized systems for gender-disaggregated data, monitoring dashboards, and GEP evaluation tools.

A notable strength of the actions selected for refinement is their cross-functionality: many combine operational, educational, and cultural change components, and several were developed collaboratively through Twin Trio co-creation groups, further reinforcing their adaptability.

The resulting future GEP structure is therefore expected to:

- Reflect both institutional diversity and shared strategic goals
- Include a balance of structural, procedural, and cultural actions
- Provide mechanisms for monitoring and updating actions in response to evolving needs
- Facilitate peer learning and replication across the European Research Area

This refined composition ensures that GEPs move beyond symbolic compliance and evolve into dynamic tools for institutional transformation, aligned with the ERA Policy Agenda and national equality frameworks.

4.5 Structure and Content of a Refined GEP

Building on the insights from the sustainability assessment and the further actions identified, the refined Gender Equality Plan adopted a modular and adaptive format structured as follows:

Strategic Vision and Institutional Commitment

Articulation of the institution's long-term equality goals

- Reference to national and EU-level policy alignment
- Endorsement by leadership and governing bodies

Analysis and Diagnosis

- Institutional data on gender distribution, pay gap, leadership representation
- Analysis of intersectional inequalities (age, nationality, disability, etc.)
- Findings from past evaluations and stakeholder consultation

Action Plan

For each GEP area, actions were listed in the following fields:

- Title and objective
- Target population
- Responsible units and stakeholders
- Intersectoral and intersectional dimensions
- Timeline and milestones
- Activities
- Output
- Outcome
- Impact
- Resources allocated
- KPI

Sustainability and Monitoring Framework

- Description of how actions are embedded into structures/processes
- Feedback loops and adaptive mechanisms
- Monitoring indicators and reporting schedule
- Integration with broader institutional strategies (e.g. HR, Research, Ethics)

Future-oriented Actions and Innovation

- Actions piloted post-NEXUS with potential scale-up
- Engagement with external stakeholders and intersectoral partners
- Contribution to national and European-level policy learning

Summary Table – Sustainable Actions by GEP Area and Partner Institution (Table 10)

Partner Institution	Work-Life Balance & Organizational Culture	Gender Balance in Leadership & Decision-Making	Gender Equality in Recruitment & Career Progression	Gender Dimension in Research & Teaching Content	Measures against Gender-Based Violence (GBV) including Sexual Harassment	Data Collection Process
TU Dublin	EDI Champions Network; EDI Info-Hub	NA	Inclusive mentoring framework	NA	Bystander Intervention Training and Awareness Online Module	NA
Frederick University	Annual Training on Gender Equality and Intersectionality (P2DF)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
UNISOFIA	NA	NA	Inclusive mentoring framework	NA	NA	Data Collection and percentage monitoring among student academics etc (related to gender, age, etc.)
University of Le Mans	Parenting Resource Group	NA	Influence of biases in Decision Making; Fostering Empowerment for Women at Work	Gender Equality and Intersectionality in research proposals	Gender, Health and Well-being	NA
AGH University	Inclusive Communication Guidelines	Information Campaign	NA	E-Course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality	NA	Fostering participation in work-related training through

						data collection with gender and intersectionality perspective. Implementation GEAM Tool
Bay Zoltan	NA	Implementation of GEAM Tool	N/A	N/A	Inclusive Communication Guidelines	NA
University of Nis	Better environment for Roma students at the faculty; Parenting Resource Group	NA	Influence of biases in Decision Making	Gender Equality and Intersectionality in research proposals	Informing employees and students about the existence of the Regulation on Prevention and Protection from Sexual Harassment	NA
IIT	NA	NA	Influence of biases in Decision Making	Gender Equality and Intersectionality in research proposals	Recognizing and addressing harassment in the workplace	NA
Koç University	NA	Skill Development Program	Inclusive mentoring framework	NA	Bystander Intervention Training and Awareness Online Module	NA

Notes:

“NA” indicates that no sustainable action emerged in the refinement phase specifically for that GEP area.

- Actions marked as “**inclusive communication,**” “**mentoring,**” or “**training**” often overlap across multiple GEP domains.

Some actions contribute to more than one area but have been placed based on primary impact focus.

5. Further and Innovative Actions

5.1 Innovative actions designed by each partner for the post project phase

Beyond the sustainability analysis of pilot actions, NEXUS partners identified a set of further and innovative actions that will extend the impact of the project beyond its formal duration. These initiatives emerged from the reflection process carried out during the refinement workshops and built directly on the lessons learned through implementation, monitoring, and evaluation.

The proposed actions address both structural gaps and emerging needs that were not fully covered by the initial pilots but are essential to consolidate the progress made. They are designed to strengthen institutional commitment towards gender equality, expand inclusivity to new dimensions (such as disability or cultural communication), and ensure that the transformative approach of NEXUS continues to evolve after the project's completion.

Importantly, these actions are aligned with the main areas of the GEP framework, including:

- Work-life balance and organizational culture
- Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
- Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
- Gender dimension in research and teaching content
- Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

The following table summarizes the further and innovative actions envisaged by each partner institution, along with the GEP areas to which they are connected. These commitments reflect the sustainability dimension of NEXUS, ensuring that gender equality strategies will continue to develop, adapt, and scale in the years to come. (Table 11)

Table 11

Partners	Further and innovative actions to be implemented after the end of the project	GEP's Area for further action
Technological University Dublin (Ireland)	A GBV policy for the university	Measures against gender base violence, including sexual harassment
Frederick University (Cyprus)	Continuation and Expansion of Annual Intersectionality-Focused Training	Work life balance and Organizational Culture
Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski (Bulgary)	Guidelines for improving work-life balance in academia	Work life balance and Organizational Culture
Le Mans University (France)	Culture of equality: innovative awareness-raising tools	Measures against gender base violence, including sexual harassment
AGH University of Krakow (Poland)	Inclusive chat-bot	Measures against gender base violence, including sexual harassment
Bay Zoltan Nonprofit Ltd for Applied Research (Hungary)	Guidance and training supporting inclusive and nonviolent communication in a professional context	Work Life Balance & Organizational Culture
University of Nis (Serbia)	Improved quality of studies for the disabled	Disability Inclusion
Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (Italy)	Inclusive Communication Guidelines	Cultural Organization and Communication
Koç University (Turkey)	Gender Equality Ambassadors Program	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making

5.1.1 Technological University of Dublin (TU Dublin)

Innovative Action: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment Policy

During the interviews, the idea that emerged as innovative further action is to complete a Gender Balance Violence and Harassment Policy that is now being developed.

Objectives: To ensure an institutional campus culture is safe, respectful, and supportive. The aim is to create a campus community in which everybody assumes responsibility for addressing sexual violence and harassment. It will promote positive behaviors around sex, which necessitates highly visible messaging and regular affirmation from senior leadership. This policy is explicitly linked to clear lines of responsibility, active responses, institutional reporting, and regular review. It will include guidelines for addressing student complaints, including transparency for all involved. Policy implementation is supported by institutional leadership, and an annual report to the Governing Authority.

GEP area of intervention: Measures against gender-based violence included sexual harassment

Intersectional Dimensions: All dimensions are included

Intersectoral Component: The Department for Higher and Further Education, the Higher Education Authority and other national bodies like the Irish University Association Ireland are involved. In addition, civil society organizations such as the Rape Crisis Network Ireland and the National Women's Council of Ireland have an advisory role. Other national bodies involved are the Union of Students.

Relevance to data collection: Reporting data gathered through the “Speak Out” self-reporting tool informs the policy development

Timeframe: From 2026 onwards

Implementation Strategy:

- Training and Education program
- School/unit-based initiatives
- Students' services
- Care and Support services
- Complaints processes

- Policy monitoring and evaluation

Expected Output: The policy is implemented through an institutional action plan, with concrete actions in the areas outlined above.

Expected Outcomes:

- Increased awareness of GBV issues among staff and students
- Increased awareness of Intervention strategies (e.g., Bystander intervention) among staff and students
- Enhanced clear and easy-to-find communication of information about support available and reporting mechanisms.

Long-term Impact: Highly sustainable as it is part of the national framework “Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions”. TU Dublin must report annually to the Higher Education Authority on the implementation of the National Framework.

Organizational Sustainability: Highly sustainable as it is part of the national framework “Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions”. TU Dublin must report annually to the Higher Education Authority on the implementation of the National Framework

Operational Sustainability: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment is a priority of the university and its EDI policy. At the EDI office, a GBV Manager is responsible for this policy. It is a full-time, permanent position.

Cultural Sustainability: Resistance to GBV action is primarily individual, rather than institutional, type of resistance and hence there are no cultural sustainability risks at present

Strategic Sustainability: The policy is embedded in a wider, national policy strategic framework

Adaptive Sustainability: The policy will be updated periodically and adapted in line with evaluation results as well as future trends.

5.1.2 Frederick University (FU)

Continuation and Expansion of Annual Intersectionality-Focused Training

Frederick University proposes extending its **annual training program on gender equality and intersectionality**, developed under NEXUS, into the post-project phase. This initiative is designed to remain dynamic and evolving, tackling new thematic areas each year, thus ensuring continuous learning and cultural transformation.

Objectives:

- To maintain momentum gained during NEXUS and embed it in the institutional culture.
- To promote a deeper understanding of intersectionality among staff and faculty.
- To inform institutional policies and improve working and learning conditions.

GEP area of intervention: Work Life Balance and Organizational Culture.

Intersectional Dimensions: The training topic can evolve annually, allowing for responsiveness to emerging societal issues (e.g., immigration, LGBTQI+, mental health), and every year it can focus on other topics such as age, language, class, sexual orientation, menopause, disability, and immigration, expanding to other intersectional dimensions.

Each training cycle will focus on one or more underrepresented or vulnerable groups, such as:

- People with disabilities
- LGBTQI+ individuals
- People with migration backgrounds
- Age and menopause-related challenges
- Class and language-based barriers

Implementation Strategy:

- The action will remain under the P2DF committee, with internal coordination by the NEXUS team and external collaboration with expert trainers.
- Annual planning meetings will determine the year's topic, resources, and format (in-person or online).
- The training will continue to be linked with policy development, such as the update of the university's Gender Equality Plan and internal regulations.
- External stakeholders will be invited to provide the training.

Expected output: At least one training course per year on gender equality and intersectionality.

Expected Outcomes:

- Awareness of Gender Equality throughout Frederick University.
- Continued capacity building among staff and faculty.
- Staff and Faculty informed about new gender equality trends in Europe and globally.

Long-term Impact:

- Institutionalization of inclusive training cycles.
- Cultural shifts toward equity, visibility of discrimination, and improved work-life balance.
- Support for national and European frameworks on gender equality in higher education.

Organizational Sustainability: This action is structurally embedded into the P2DF Committee's annual training cycle and is repeated every semester.

Operational Sustainability: The lead member of the NEXUS team also leads one of the sub-groups of the P2DF committee.

Cultural Sustainability: This action will promote the culture of equity and diversity and the coexistence of different ways of life.

Strategic Sustainability: The lead member of the NEXUS team also leads one of the sub-groups of the P2DF committee. The action could become a replicable model for other institutions in Cyprus.

Adaptive Sustainability: The training content can be flexible, and this ensures continued relevance and engagement across different segments of the university population. Every year the content can approach a new intersectional dimension and address mainstream topics and adapt to social trends (i.e. immigration, biography, sexual orientation, etc.).

5.1.3 Sofia University (UNISOFIA)

Sofia University proposes the following innovative further action: **“Guidelines for improving work-life balance in academia”**. The objective is to enhance the ability to effectively manage the demands of academic work (research, teaching, administrative duties) and personal life, ensuring overall well-being and fulfillment.

Innovative Action: Development of Guidelines for Improving Work-Life Balance in Academia

Objective: To foster a healthier balance between academic responsibilities (teaching, research, administration) and personal life for university staff, contributing to both professional productivity and individual well-being.

GEP Area of Intervention: Work-life balance and organizational culture.

Intersectional Dimensions: The action considers varying needs based on gender identity, age, family status, and caregiving responsibilities.

Implementation Strategy:

- Drafting guidelines in collaboration with the HR Department and the University Center for Psychological Counseling and Research.
- Validation by the Ethics Committee and endorsement by university leadership.
- Internal dissemination and publication on the institutional website.

Timeframe: October 2025 – October 2026.

Expected output: A pdf document representing a guideline to be published on the Sofia University website.

Expected Outcomes:

- Staff and faculty will have structured support for managing time, setting boundaries, and ensuring mental well-being.
- Organizational awareness and resources for balancing professional and personal roles will improve.

Long-term Impact:

- A more sustainable academic environment, leading to reduced burnout and improved job satisfaction.
- Institutional alignment with EU and national priorities on mental health, inclusiveness, and workplace quality.

Organizational Sustainability: Formal inclusion in HR policies and strategic documents.

Operational Sustainability: It can be maintained by implementing workflows and resource management systems.

Cultural Sustainability: Fostering a campus culture that values flexibility, mutual respect, and mental health.

Strategic Sustainability: Developing long-term institutional strategies that integrate work-life balance initiatives into academic planning

Adaptive Sustainability: Will evolve with feedback from users and changes in academic working conditions.

5.1.4 Le Mans University (UM)

Le Mans University proposes the following innovative further action; **“Culture of Equality: Innovative Awareness-Raising Tools”**. The objective is to develop creative and participatory tools to raise awareness around gender equality, intersectionality, and discrimination, especially targeting students.

GEP area of intervention: Measures against GBV including sexual harassment.

Objectives: spreading and embedding a culture of equality

Intersectional Dimensions: Disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, religion/belief, age

Implementation Strategy: The action will combine interactive workshops for the creation of awareness-raising tools (e.g. computer modules, short videos and quizzes to be distributed by e-mail and via the internal website videos, infographics), and the distribution of these tools to the university population. The aim is to foster critical reflection on social norms and discrimination. Focus will be given to reaching students and underrepresented groups through engaging, context-sensitive formats.

Expected output: Fun, short, visible awareness-raising tools that will reach a wider community than just the people already interested in the subject who go looking for information. A targeted newsletter (e-mail, pop-up internal site)

Time Frame: Fall 2025- June 2026

Expected Outcome: a dozen tools distributed throughout the year to the university community.

Long Term Impact: A greater culture of equality, reaching people who don't look for information on their own.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is supported by the network of equalities correspondents, itself perpetuated in the GEP.

Operational Sustainability: The action is developed at the time planned for the network of equalities correspondents.

Cultural Sustainability: The action aims to develop a culture of equality.

Strategic Sustainability: The action is made visible by a good communication strategy.

Adaptive Sustainability: The tools developed will be adapted to the context and the needs.

5.1.5 AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH)

AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH) proposes the following innovative further action **“Inclusive chat-bot”**. The objective is to raise awareness about inclusive communication, and to make internal communication more diverse and diverse.

Innovative Action: Guidance and training supporting inclusive and nonviolent communication in a professional context

Objective: The objective is to raise awareness about inclusive communication, to make internal communication more diverse and diversity

GEP Area of Intervention: Measures against gender-based violence included sexual harassment

Intersectional dimensions beyond gender: age, profession, socio-economic status, position within university; sexual orientation

Intersectoral component: Collaborate on the development of a chatbot with an external company to implement the technology at AGH.

Implementation Strategy:

- Designing and developing an educational and informational conversational bot.
- Creating content for thematic conversation paths: inspiration, support, events, recommended interventions (institutions) and recommended media.
- Conduct user testing with AGH students in the form of focus groups.
- Implementing chatbot on university platforms (e.g., GEP website)
- Promoting the tool within the university community through campaigns and materials.

Timeframe: April 2025 - April 2026

Expected output:

- A fully functional equality bot is available 24/7 for students.
- Five structured conversational pathways providing:
 - practical guidance on reporting discrimination,
 - inspirational content (quotes, quizzes, stories),
 - information on available psychological, legal, and financial support,
 - updates on GEP-related events,
 - recommended podcasts and media.

Expected Outcomes:

- Increased awareness among students and staff about discrimination, equality measures, and available support mechanisms at AGH.
- Improved accessibility of support resources through an anonymous and user-friendly digital tool.

Long-term Impact: A more inclusive, safe, and equality-conscious academic environment at AGH, supported by a strengthened institutional response to discrimination and inequality.

Organizational Sustainability: It is planned to be embedded in the official communication channels of the AGH platforms, with the support of the IT Sector Unit after the piloting phase proves the safety and usability of the solution.

Operational Sustainability: Upon implementation, AGH as a technical university has the capability to maintain it due to many IT-support units available.

Cultural Sustainability: The chat-bot is intersectional by design as it promotes diversity in all aspects (ethnicity, age, gender, etc.).

Strategic Sustainability: The chat bot is a part of AGH GEP 2025-2028 and is supported by the Dean of Faculty of Humanities and the Rector of AGH.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is research-based and as such is prone to experiments and potential failures as well as to redesign. This is an innovative aspect of the action.

5.1.6 Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (BZN)

Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research proposes the following innovative further action “**Guidance and training supporting inclusive and nonviolent communication in a professional context**”. The objective is to train staff in nonviolent and inclusive communication.

Innovative Action: Guidance and training supporting inclusive and nonviolent communication in a professional context.

Objective: The objective is to train staff in nonviolent and inclusive communication.

GEP Area of Intervention:

- Work-life balance and organizational culture.
- Measures against gender-based violence included sexual harassment.

Intersectional dimensions beyond gender: Age and socioeconomic background.

Intersectoral component: Consultation with communication experts from the NGO sector.

Implementation Strategy:

- Program planned and presented to management (Oct-Nov 2025).
- The program is inserted in the annual training plan for 2026, with funding secured (Dec 2025).
- NGO communication expert engaged in consultation sessions to plan jointly the content of the 1-day training program.
- Training is scheduled for 2026, participants recruited through division directors and department heads (Jan-Feb 2026).
- Training is delivered.
- Feedback sought from participants via event feedback.

Timeframe: First run in 2026 and replicated in 2027 until the next update of the GEP (dependent on the availability of funding).

Expected output: 20 researchers and research managers trained in 2026; program replicated in 2027 (dependent on the availability of funding).

Expected Outcomes: Based and extended on the scope of the inclusive communication guidelines produced in NEXUS, annually 20 key employees will be trained in the areas of inclusive and nonviolent communication, applying the principles in their everyday work.

Long-term Impact:

- Improved organizational culture in the areas of inclusivity and communication.

- Improved satisfaction of employees working with trained colleagues.
- Improved retention of staff within the organization.

Organizational Sustainability: This is yet to be tested, as it is a pilot area for the organization. However, we have had similar communication training before, with a more limited scope, which was successful.

Operational Sustainability: Operationally the action is sustainable; replication supported by the low efforts repeating the action following the first run, even if changes and adjustments are needed. The only significant risk is the available financial resources, which are earmarked and verified annually (no longer-term commitment is possible now).

Cultural Sustainability: The action is already an extension of Action 4 of NEXUS, with an added training element. The action will be a pilot, therefore strongly dependent on interim evaluation after the first round and decision / redesign (if needed) on how it will be run subsequently.

Strategic Sustainability: The action will be a pilot, therefore strongly dependent on interim evaluation after the first round and decision / redesign (if needed) on how it will be run subsequently.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is adaptable to changing priorities by editing the training content; but as it is designed now, it is dependent on the availability of funding.

5.1.7 University of Nis (UN)

University of Nis proposes the following innovative further action: **“Improved quality of studies for the disabled”**. The objective is to improve hardware and equipment conditions for disabled.

Innovative Action: Improved quality of studies for the disabled.

Objective: The objective is to improve hardware and equipment conditions for disabled.

GEP Area of Intervention: A new area of interest: Disability Inclusion that can be included in the GEP area “Work-life Balance and Organizational Culture”.

Implementation Strategy:

- Review of the most important types of needs of students and staff at the faculty.
- Identify technical hardware necessary to help with identified needs.
- Perform a market analysis to determine the costs and steps necessary for the implementation.

Timeframe: February 2026 – December 2026.

Expected output: A marketing analysis report.

Expected Outcomes: Determined steps and relevant costs to upgrade equipment and facilities for better conditions for the disabled.

Long-term Impact: Better conditions for disabled at UN.

Organizational Sustainability: Management commitment necessary.

Operational Sustainability: Low cost for the analysis phase.

Cultural Sustainability: Fosters internal dialogue.

Strategic Sustainability: Aligned with inclusivity of disabled policy.

Adaptive Sustainability: Additional funding may be required, but donors can be identified and approached for such exact projects, once identified.

5.1.8 Fondazione Istituto italiano di Tecnologia (IIT)

Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia proposes the following innovative further action; **“Inclusive Communication Guidelines”**. The objective is to address and eliminate discriminatory language and stereotypes.

Innovative Action: Inclusive Communication Guidelines”.

Objective: The objective is to address and eliminate discriminatory language and stereotypes.

GEP Area of Intervention: A new area of interest: Cultural Organization and Communication.

Intersectional Dimensions: The guidelines include not just gender, but also race, age, disability, and other diverse dimensions.

Implementation Strategy:

- First draft of the guidelines with an intersectional approach.
- Validation by HR Director and Communication Director.
- Approval by top management.

Internal dissemination activity.

Timeframe: October 2025 – October 2026.

Expected output: A pdf document guideline published on the IIT intranet.

Expected Outcomes: Cultural and organizational opportunities.

Long-term Impact: Improvement of internal and external communication style regarding inclusive language by IIT staff.

Organizational Sustainability: Coordinated by the D&I Office in collaboration with HR and Communication teams.

Operational Sustainability: Implemented with internal resources and digital platforms; low-cost and scalable.

Cultural Sustainability: Reinforces inclusive practices at all levels of institutional communication.

Strategic Sustainability: Supports IIT’s long-term commitment to responsible communication and public image.

Adaptive Sustainability: Guidelines will be periodically revised to reflect feedback and evolving language standards.

5.1.9 Koç University (KU)

Koç University proposes the following innovative further action; “**Gender Equality Ambassadors Program**”. The objective is to enhance the ability to effectively manage the demands of academic work (research, teaching, administrative duties) and personal life, ensuring overall well-being and fulfillment.

Innovative Action: Development of Guidelines for Improving Work-Life Balance in Academia.

Objective: Promoting inclusive and gender-sensitive practices through trained ambassadors embedded in academic and administrative units, acting as contact points.

GEP Area of Intervention:

- Measure against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.
- Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.
- Gender balance in leadership and decision-making.
- Work-life balance and organizational culture.

Intersectional Dimensions: There is an intersectional dimension because the action includes age, language, marital status, caregiving roles, socioeconomic status, and citizenship.

Intersectoral Component: There is an intersectoral dimension because the program can be extended to include ambassadors from industry and alumni networks to promote knowledge transfer and multi-sectoral learning. The program fosters collaboration across academic and administrative units and can be expanded to include ambassadors from industry, civil society, and alumni networks. By engaging stakeholders beyond the university, it supports the transfer of gender equality practices across sectors and promotes mutual learning on inclusive workplace culture, recruitment, and leadership.

Implementation Strategy:

- Develop training curriculum and ambassador role description.
- Recruit one volunteer per unit.
- Deliver core training.
- Facilitate coordination via biannual meetings and a digital hub.
- Equipment of ambassadors with protocols and resources.

Timeframe:

- Pilot: 2025–2026.

- Full rollout: 2026–2027.

Expected output:

- Ambassador roster.
- Awareness of events materials.
- Event coordination.
- Impact report.

Expected Outcomes:

- Increased visibility of gender issues at unit level.
- Quick response to localized concerns.
- Enhanced sense of inclusion and ownership.

Long Term Impact:

- Strengthens the institutional culture of care and shared responsibility.
- Build bridges between central gender equality efforts and everyday practice.
- Ambassadors help decentralize gender equality efforts, serving as eyes and ears on the ground.
- increase responsiveness to micro-level gender issues.

Organizational Sustainability: The action embeds gender equality into day-to-day operations and distributed leadership.

Operational Sustainability: The action requires light-touch coordination after setup; ambassadors can operate within their units.

Cultural Sustainability: The action builds trust and peer engagement and supports behavioral change.

Strategic Sustainability: The action is aligned with GEP aims and helps embed gender equality in institutional structures.

Adaptive Sustainability: Ambassadors can evolve their role based on local needs and ongoing university priorities.

5.2 Replicability Potential and Expected Impact

The further actions proposed by NEXUS partners as part of the GEP refinement process reflect a forward-looking and highly contextualized approach to institutional transformation. Designed to be implemented after the project's conclusion, these actions respond to local needs while addressing transversal challenges such as inclusive communication, GBV prevention, leadership accountability, work-life balance, and intersectional mentoring.

A key insight emerging from the analysis is that **replicability increases when further actions are embedded in permanent roles, policy frameworks, or digital platforms**, reducing reliance on individual champions. Actions that incorporate **intersectional approaches**, such as inclusive mentoring, GBV prevention, and equitable communication, are particularly suited for replication across diverse institutional types.

Despite the contextual nature of many actions, several display a strong potential for adaptation and replication across institutions with similar organizational profiles or strategic goals. This potential is enhanced when actions are:

- low-cost and modular
- rooted in internal consultation processes
- aligned with national and EU-level priorities (e.g., Horizon Europe, SDGs) or anchored in existing institutional frameworks (e.g., HR, Research Office, Communication).

If systematically adopted and sustained, these further actions have the capacity to:

- promote inclusive and safe academic environments
- improve organizational processes through intersectional awareness
- enhance the institutionalization of equality beyond compliance
- and serve as models for policy experimentation and diffusion at European level.

6. Annexes

6.1 Detailed sustainability assessment criteria (organizational, operational, cultural, strategic, adaptive)

6.1.1 Technological University of Dublin (TU Dublin)

Technological University of Dublin (TUD) instead of conducting an analysis session for the refinement of the GEP, carried out four separate interviews with four key individuals: the Gender Balance Violence (GBV) Lead, the Researcher Career Development Manager, the Athena Swan Lead, and the Senior Equity, Diversity Inclusion (EDI) Manager. The interviews provide very rich information about the sustainability of each NEXUS inclusive at TU Dublin, covering different aspects (organizational sustainability, adaptability, replicability/scalability, inclusiveness, risks and mitigations). The GEP refinement process at TU Dublin was structured around five pilot actions initiated during the NEXUS implementation phase. The institutional team reflected the feasibility, scalability, and long-term relevance of each action. This analysis confirmed that all five actions have potential for sustainability and institutional embedding.

Four actions (1, 2, 3 and 5) were deemed to be highly sustainable and will continue after the end of the NEXUS project, with refinements expected to be made to integrate implementation lessons and adapt to evolving circumstances. While difficulties may be encountered in the future, these actions are firmly embedded in university priorities, strategy frameworks and policies, and this acts as a guarantee of permanence. On the other hand, the sustainability of action 4 (EDI Info Hub) will depend on resources invested in making sure that the EDI info-hub is continuously updated (a person dedicated to this task will need to be put in place). During the analysis sessions, participants individuated also the innovative further action to be implemented after the end of the project named **“Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment Policy”**.

First Key Sustainable Action Identified for GEP’s Refinement: Gender Based Violence (GBV) Training and Awareness Online Module

GEP area of intervention: Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment.

Objective: Develop a skill and knowledge-based online module to educate and raise awareness on GBV and provide strategies that will both deal with and combat GBV in partner institutions and beyond. TU Dublin has committed to making this training part of its EDI culture.

Organizational Sustainability: Sustainability ensured as action is firmly embedded in EDI priorities and policies at the university, in particular “Ending sexual violence and harassment”.

Operational Sustainability: The module will be kept on the EDI website as well as other places such as the TU Dublin e-learning platform, as well as being integrated into online training, so that it is easily accessible to the university. Furthermore, the action is expected to be sustainable in the long term, because the information included in that module is not really going to change. The action is cost-efficient and deliverable through a standardized, train-the-trainer approach, with internal facilitators identified. The risk is not being aware of the many different factors and biases of all communities.

Cultural Sustainability: It will be crucial to have an allyship with the different communities at the university. Within the travelling community, for example, for a young woman to stand up and speak out about sexual violence has massive consequences outside of the university. And to expect them to do that by just saying that is the policy, it is not OK. The same goes for the black community. TUD cannot say to them that these are the rules without taking into consideration all the external ripples that can cause or the potential consequences. It is needed to ally with the communities and ask them about the best way to implement policies and actions. It is crucial to be aware of the many different factors and biases. Training fosters dialogue around power, responsibility, and safety, reinforcing institutional values of care and inclusion.

Strategic Sustainability: It will be crucial to have an allyship with the different communities at the university. Supports national HE goals (e.g. HEA Gender Action Plan) and TU Dublin’s own EDI Strategic Plan.

Adaptive Sustainability: The module is highly adaptable as it is not just on sexual violence, it can be adapted to bullying, to harassment, to racism. Furthermore, it doesn't require a specialized trainer to deliver it. It can be slotted into different learning environments for both staff and students.

Second and Third Key Sustainable Actions Identified for GEP’s Refinement:

Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis and Inclusive Mentoring Handbook for Career Progression and Success

GEP area of intervention: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

Objective: 1) To ascertain the baseline needs in relation to mentoring in the partner institutions and to subsequently develop a mentoring program; 2) To develop a training program/manual for mentors with inclusivity at its core using the data gathered in the action “Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis”.

Organizational Sustainability: Actions 2 and 3 consist of the implementation of recommendations on inclusive mentoring in the mentoring program. This action is quite sustainable from the structural (organizational) point of view, because the mentoring program is in the Researcher Career Development Framework at TU Dublin. This Framework is part of the human resources strategy for researchers. Action 3 (the handbook) is also part of our Athena Swan commitments, which strengthens the sustainability of the action. The mentoring model is now being coordinated across faculties, with support from Graduate Studies and EDI teams. The action is Integrated into internal communication guidelines and supported by the Communications Department.

Operational Sustainability: From the resources point of view, there is a permanent member of staff responsible for the implementation of this action. The main risk is what will happen when the program gets bigger and more complicated to manage. We could then have an issue due to lack of human resources. The main challenge of this action is for me implement all the recommendations included in the handbook. Now the program is totally voluntary, and there is no concrete benefit for mentors to join the program. The mitigation would be to offer them something, such as timetable hours. Processes for mentor–mentee matching, evaluation, and feedback have been outlined and tested. The Toolkit is downloadable and disseminated online; updates require minimal resources.

Cultural Sustainability: Increasing the diversity of the pool of mentors and mentees is a challenge. But first, TUD needs to know which are the grounds for discrimination that need to focus on and that are missing in the program. If TUD doesn’t know the data, then they can’t tackle a lack of inclusivity. The action helped normalize mentoring practices and opened dialogue on power dynamics, support, and career equity. Promotes critical reflection on everyday language and helps shift organizational norms.

Strategic Sustainability: This action can be easily replicated. For example, the inclusive mentoring program could be extended to academic staff. As for professional staff, there is already a mentoring program set in place, and the recommendations for inclusive mentoring could absolutely be replicated in that program. It must strive for inclusivity among all the different mentoring programs in the university. Tied to talent development, research excellence, and retention strategies. Aligns with TU Dublin's commitment to inclusive communication and broader HE sectors guidance.

Adaptive Sustainability: Regarding the adaptability of the action in relation to changes (whether internal or external) there are no major risks, given that the action is embedded in university frameworks. Excellence in research, being competitive in that regard, is all about nurturing our researchers, making sure that they develop and enhance their skills while they are at TU Dublin. That is why the mentoring program is so relevant to researchers, and TUD needs to be research focused. Flexible formats (peer, cross-disciplinary, short-term) allow tailoring to individual needs and life stages. Toolkit content can be easily revised and expanded based on user feedback and evolving terminology.

Fourth Key Sustainable Actions Identified for GEP's Refinement: EDI Info-Hub

GEP area of intervention: Work Life Balance & Organizational Culture.

Objective: To increase awareness of EDI initiatives, resources, and policy throughout the institution.

Organizational Sustainability: There are no risks now regarding organizational sustainability. However, the EDI Director post is vacant at present, and TUD will need to see the new direction after this post has been filled. A dedicated communication stream is now established through the Research and Innovation Office.

Operational Sustainability: The main risk of the Info-Hub is that it requires manpower to constantly update it. TUD needs to make sure that they have a staff member responsible for the action, otherwise it will not be sustainable. We need somebody for that role, and that role is recognized as part of their work. The action uses low-cost digital tools and can be implemented regularly (e.g. monthly highlights).

Cultural Sustainability: There are no major issues, especially in relation to inclusivity as the direction of policy is towards intersectionality, and the Info-Hub covers different discrimination

grounds. Helps counter invisibility and promote role models for students and early-career researchers.

Strategic Sustainability: The Info Hub will be particularly useful for schools at TUD university that are going for Athena Swan. One way to ensure sustainability in this regard is that different schools have an area on their page that works as an info hub as well, because all that EDI information might be useful to have up on their respective websites with our central EDI Info-Hub linked up to it. Supports research culture reform and contributes to international visibility and rankings.

Adaptive Sustainability: See strategic sustainability. It can include intersectional stories (e.g. by ethnicity, disability, LGBTQI+) and be expanded to podcasts or videos.

Fifth Key Sustainable Actions Identified for GEP's Refinement: EDI Champions Network

GEP area of intervention: Work Life Balance & Organizational Culture.

Objective: To create an EDI champion network throughout TU Dublin thus embedding individuals who:

- Have an interest in, and commitment to, advancing equality, diversity and inclusion within their department and, where appropriate, across the University.
- Are familiar with how to access or get advice on relevant policies, procedures and legislation.
- Are a visible and proactive Champion of EDI within their department/unit.

Organizational Sustainability: Action is sustainable insofar as it is on our institutional action plan from 2022 to 2025. And the expectation is that this action will continue into the next action plan, but in terms of policy at the university. There is a risk to this action. The question is whether a new leadership would consider it worth it. Process integrated into GEP review cycles and Athena Swan submissions; driven by EDI governance structures.

Operational Sustainability: A big barrier has been that we can't really compensate people for their time in any sort of meaningful way, so people are volunteering to act as Champions. That also means that you can't hold too much over them in what you expect them to do. So, what is needed is more formal recognition and a budget for this role. There is a commitment at the institutional level. Uses existing consultation and feedback loops, no major additional cost.

Cultural Sustainability: An intersectional approach is built into the action, but more could be done in terms of ensuring inclusivity. What you don't want is that the only people who are volunteering their time as EDI champions are people who have characteristics that are marginalized in some way, because then you're just adding to their labor and you're assigning them responsibility for that kind of work. Strengthens the culture of shared responsibility and learning across stakeholders.

Strategic Sustainability: Champions networks at the university are trying to work together in getting recognized as champions, which is crucial, because working together across different functions within the institution really helps in supporting this kind of network. There are other things that can help overcome barriers. The work that employee engagement is doing, for example, to recognize all their Champions. Regarding replicability, there are champions or ambassadors for other types of other areas. Enables data-informed and context-specific planning; increases institutional resilience.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action was designed from the beginning to be adaptable in the face of external or internal changes. There's potential for replicability. The action was designed from the beginning to be adaptable. Regarding the impact of the action, there's a lot of focus on impact and so we must recognize that some of these are not very easily measurable. Designed to be iterative and responsive, allowing the GEP to evolve with institutional realities.

6.1.2 Frederick University (FredU)

Frederick University held the analysis session for GEP's Refinement on 3 June 2025. Participants were four people, all females, two members of the Gender Equality Committee and two members of NEXUS Team. The team discussed the implementation of the NEXUS pilot actions, the sustainability of each action, and further steps to follow. The sustainability analysis conducted by Frederick University as part of their GEP refinement process demonstrates a strong institutional commitment to maintaining and expanding the impact of NEXUS pilot actions. The analysis followed the multidimensional framework provided by the project methodology, encompassing organizational, operational, cultural, strategic, and adaptive dimensions of sustainability.

In addition, it was decided that an effort will be made that the action **“Annual training from an external speaker on Gender Equality and Intersectionality under the Personal and Professional Committee (P2DF)”** is included in the Second Gender Equality Plan (GEP) of the University.

The discussion will be continued towards the end of the year that the ATHENA Swan Application will be near to submission and the first FredU GEP will be expired.

It is also expected that GEAM survey will be launch for a third time in four years.

During the analysis sessions, participants individuated also the innovative further action to be implemented after the end of the project: **“Continuation and Expansion of Annual Intersectionality-Focused Training “**

Key Sustainable Action Identified for GEP's Refinement:

Annual training from an external speaker on Gender Equality and Intersectionality, embedded in the university's **Personal and Professional Development Framework (P2DF)**.

GEP area of intervention: Work Life Balance and Organizational Culture.

Organizational Sustainability: This action is structurally embedded into the P2DF Committee's annual training cycle and is supported by top management and a dedicated sub-group led by a NEXUS team member. The university has committed to repeating the training each academic year (every semester).

Operational Sustainability: The action can be scaled up or replicated to specific departments, or other segments of the population or other institutions. Currently the action is offered to the general

population of the university. Recently a MoU was signed between the 13 universities of Cyprus to promote GE. This step might help support this type of action.

Cultural Sustainability: Every year a new intersectional dimension can be proposed (immigration, language, class, sexual orientation, and others). This action will promote the culture of equity and diversity and the coexistence of different ways of life. It is well received by participants and can contribute to normalizing conversations on diversity and equity.

Strategic Sustainability: Given that the same internal resources and committee structures are used each year, and that the training is low-cost when local speakers are involved, the action is financially and logistically feasible. Some risks of the action might be the financial support especially if the speaker is not from Cyprus.

Adaptive Sustainability: The training content can be flexible, and this ensures continued relevance and engagement across different segments of the university's population. Every year the training can be addressed to mainstream topics and adapted to social trends. As this action falls under the priorities of the university (training offered to academic and administrative personnel), it will be resilient to potential changes.

6.1.3 Sofia University (UNISOFIA)

Sofia University held the analysis session for GEP's Refinement on 4 June 2025. Participants were four people, all females, 3 project managers and an Associate Professor. The agenda was not detailed.

The team discussed the future development of the NEXUS pilot actions, both regarding the GEP's refinement and further action to develop after the end of the project.

Sofia University conducted a robust GEP refinement process focusing on the sustainability of actions related to inclusive data monitoring and mentoring for career progression. The analysis sessions demonstrated how institutional reflexivity and commitment to long-term structural change can shape a sustainable equality agenda.

The team analyzed all 5 NEXUS pilot actions, and it was decided that an effort will be made for the following two actions: **“Data collection and percentage monitoring among students, PhDs, academic and administrative staff in Sofia University (related to gender, age, socioeconomic status)”** and **“Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success (enhancing/ improving the existing Mentoring program)”**.

During the analysis sessions, participants individuated also the innovative further action to be implemented after the end of the project: **“Guidelines for improving work-life balance in academia”**.

First Key Sustainable Action: Data Collection and Monitoring on Gender, Age, and Socioeconomic Status

GEP area of intervention: none.

Data Collection Process: the action is aimed at improving the data collection process.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is an instrument for maintaining a reflexive gender equality and diversity policy in Sofia University; it is supported by the University management and the departments/ structures involved and it is fully embedded in institutional structures, with collaboration across several departments including Human Resources, Doctoral Studies, and Data Analysis. It forms part of a broader effort to institutionalize gender equality and diversity monitoring.

Operational Sustainability: The action is highly replicable without any specific or dedicated costs. The action could be replicated in other institutions, ecosystems, and others. It is a sustainable system for collecting data on gender equality and diversity policy with low-effort maintenance. The

action leverages internal expertise and existing infrastructure. The system is designed to run annually starting in 2025, becoming a standard operational routine.

Cultural Sustainability: The action informs practices and policies that promote inclusion. Regular data analysis is intended to drive evidence-based change, fostering a culture of transparency and accountability in recruitment, promotion, and leadership. By designing targeted policies and practices to the problems/inequalities detected, the action could help strengthen the University's reputation as an inclusive educational institution and workplace. Its intersectional focus ensures alignment with the dynamic needs of the academic community.

Strategic Sustainability: This is a strategic investment in creating a more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable university community. Its integration into long-term planning confirms its value beyond project duration. The action can be maintained over time with adaptation and upgrading. The action can be maintained over time with adaptation and upgrading. No risks are anticipated if data collection and processing continue to be socially responsible.

Adaptive Sustainability: The system is designed to be flexible and responsive to demographic shifts, leadership changes, or evolving university priorities. The action is adaptable to new challenges and opportunities related to the dynamics of the University context. The action should not be affected by changes in leadership and funding.

Generally, the action is sustainable because it is a strategic investment in creating a more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable university community.

Second Key Sustainable Action: Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success

GEP area of intervention: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

Organizational Sustainability: This enhanced mentoring program is aligned with university policies and fully supported institutionally. It offers a structured framework that fosters inclusive academic environments.

Operational Sustainability: Guidelines and evaluation mechanisms are in place to ensure consistent quality and adaptability. Mentoring processes are designed to be low-cost and scalable. Operational sustainability is reachable by integrating regular evaluation and feedback mechanisms. The intersectional aspect has been included. The action is highly replicable without any dedicated or specific costs. The action could be replicated in other institutions and ecosystems.

Cultural Sustainability: This action supports cultural transformation by enhancing the diversity and inclusiveness of mentorship, benefiting both mentors and mentees, and contributing to a more diverse and equitable workforce. The Mentoring program has been helping PhD students/ young researchers acquire new skills and better organize their research activities and engagements within the university. Regularly improving it will help them advance their careers in a holistic, supportive, and quality manner. Intersectional aspects have been included.

Strategic Sustainability: The program is integral to strategic goals for talent development and inclusion. It addresses the specific needs of PhD students and early-career researchers, particularly those from underrepresented backgrounds. The action can be maintained over time with adaptation and upgrading. Ongoing improvement of the Mentoring program, and establishing a culture of inclusion supporting mentoring relationships, could both ensure strategic sustainability. The risks of the action are lack of a sufficient number of specialists involved in the mentoring process who are equally adequate to the high demands in an academic environment and the needs of industry/business; lack of sufficient interest among PhD students/ young researchers.

Adaptive Sustainability: Designed to evolve with the academic landscape, the program addresses changing student needs and can integrate feedback from external stakeholders such as industry or civil society organizations. The program could be further adapted, improved, and extended to answer diverse student profiles, needs and career aspirations, as well as the changing market requirements. The Mentoring program should cater to diverse student profiles, needs and career aspirations, and be reflexive to the (changing) requirements of industry/business.

Generally, the action is sustainable because it could provide a better and researchers' needs-oriented Mentorship program that will help mentees advance their careers in a holistic, supportive, and quality manner.

6.1.4 Le Mans University (UM)

Le Mans University held the analysis session for GEP's refinement on 16 May 2025. Participants were five people, all females, including gender equality officers, project managers, academic staff, administrative staff, and members of the COLOURS team (two professors, an administrative employee and two project managers). The session was aimed at reassessing the effectiveness and sustainability of pilot actions implemented under NEXUS and to define how these initiatives could be incorporated into the next GEP cycle. Le Mans University refined **five key actions** implemented under the NEXUS project. Following a structured evaluation and sustainability workshop, **all actions were considered for continuation and embedded into the next institutional Gender Equality Plan (2025–2027)**.

The session provided a structured opportunity for reflection, feedback, and forward planning. It leveraged the formative evaluations carried out during the implementation phase, offering both a summative perspective and a strategic rethinking of future gender equality actions at the university. The key objective was to ensure that pilot actions do not end with the project but instead evolve into structural and sustainable components of institutional transformation. The session was designed and facilitated using the methodology and templates developed by the NEXUS project, which guided the structured reflection on:

- The outcomes and limitations of the five NEXUS pilot actions.
- The cultural, operational, and strategic sustainability of these actions.
- Possible redesigns or adaptations to increase relevance and impact.
- The identification of innovative and inclusive post-project action.

The session consisted of several phases:

1. **Introduction to NEXUS** and its pilot actions.
2. **Sustainability assessment**, using a multidimensional framework.
3. **Design of a new post-project action**.
4. **Conclusion and synthesis of recommendations**.

The outcomes of the workshop directly informed the finalization of the new **2025–2027 GEP**, which was approved by the Board of Directors on **June 12, 2025**. **All five NEXUS actions were included in the plan**, either as continued or institutionalized practices.

Below is an analysis of their sustainability using the multidimensional framework provided by the project.

First Key Sustainable Action: Influences of bias in decision making

GEP area of intervention: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

Objective: To raise awareness and understanding of gender-based discrimination, intersectionality, and sexual harassment across the university community through a mandatory online training module.

Organizational Sustainability: The action has been institutionalized: the training took place live with trainers, and some resources related to the topic are available in the toolkit on the equality mission page to keep up to date as self-training. The goal is to repeat this training regularly (every two years) to reach new staff, new employees, but also HR staff who are already trained and need reminders. An e-learning module could be set up with the materials of the training to make it more adaptable. Also, updates will be provided considering any changes in policies.

Operational Sustainability: The training should be done every year or every two years. The larger training open to everyone could be done easily because it is run by Angéline Etiemble, a sociologist working in NEXUS and in the Gender Equality Mission. The one delivered by a training company for the HR department will need to be paid again, but an e-learning module could be set up to pay for one time. The HR Department can integrate the training into onboarding processes.

Cultural Sustainability: It helps normalize discussions on equality and intersectionality and is a visible institutional signal of commitment to an inclusive culture. It is an interest in biases in the university community, a wheel to fight them. It improves the culture of inclusion at the University and addresses intersectional dimensions.

Strategic Sustainability: The training supports university compliance with national regulations and contributes to strategic goals related to inclusivity. It is highly recommended to form the HR department regularly and maintain overtime. Two risks are highlighted: 1) the quality of the training could be judged not good by the participants with a reduction in the number of participants; 2) the risk that people don't use the tools and resources made available online. The first risk could be mitigated with a post-test questionnaire to gather feedback and improve the content. The second

risk could be mitigated by promoting the university toolbox continuously through good communication.

Adaptive Sustainability: The content can be updated regularly to address evolving societal concerns (e.g. racism, LGBTQI+ issues, ableism). The form of the training can change the content too thanks to the feedback of the participants. If an e-learning course is set up, the action will be able to adapt to future changes. In the meantime, resources are available in the toolbox on the Equality Mission website.

Generally, this action is considered sustainable because it is not difficult to put in place; it is not expensive since training can be delivered by internal trainers or by contents available online.

Second Key Sustainable Action: Gender Plus Dimension in Research.

GEP area of intervention: Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content.

Objective: To integrate gender equality and inclusion of content into research and teaching content.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is led by the GEP officer, and it is supported by institutional and managerial roles. The training and the presentation of the guidelines are relayed by the different laboratories and the doctoral center; communication is made by the Communication Department.

Operational Sustainability: The action is provided by the Gender Equality Mission, and no funding is needed. The guidelines can evolve with new findings and new policies. The form of the training which accompanies the guidelines too. The guide could be distributed more widely, beyond the laboratories of the university of Le Mans.

Cultural Sustainability: Reinforces inclusive values and has an intersectional dimension. Interest in the subject encourages responsible and innovative research practices in the EU framework. The guidelines help researchers to change their perspectives and find out how to integrate gender dimensions in their research work.

Strategic Sustainability: It is aligned with the university's Equality and Diversity Charter, European Commission priorities and supports long-term cultural transformation. The action can be maintained over time. The biggest risk would be an anti-EDI movement in the laboratories and

resistance to this theme in general. To mitigate risks, it is planned to talk to researchers, try to make them understand the benefits of this action, and adapt the guide and training to their feedback.

Adaptive Sustainability: Guidelines and training can be updated with policy changes and user feedback and evolve with new findings and new policies. As it is provided by the gender equality mission, no funding is needed. Generally, this action is sustainable because it has no costs and researchers are interested in the subject.

Third Key Sustainable Action: Parenting Resource Group.

GEP area of intervention: Work Life Balance and Organizational Culture.

Objective: to reach a good work-life balance in the institution by improving the parenting organization culture.

Organizational Sustainability: This action is supported by institutional and managerial roles. Different services are involved in the theme (it is the social action of the HR Department) and supported by the Sustainable Development and Social Responsibility Unit. The GEP recommends 2 to 3 informative events per year.

Operational Sustainability: Different services of the university are working on it, including the gender equality mission. The action is provided by the Gender Equality Mission, and no funding is needed. Some of the actions proposed by the working group are not free of charge (such as calling on outside service providers to create an awareness-raising theater). However, other actions are free of charge, such as informative events with the presence of external partners (associations) who come on a voluntary basis. The action is very flexible. The activities are for all the university community. Originally, it was for parents, but it was open to caregivers also and all the people who needed a better work-life balance.

Cultural Sustainability: A need for a better work-life balance. Some people are beginning to understand that parenthood and caregiving do not just belong to the private sphere, that they also belong to the public sphere, that they can have an impact on the workplace, and that the role of the university is to help them deal with these issues and make them aware of their rights. The action is already intersectional.

Strategic Sustainability: The action is an axis of the GEP. At least one informative event should be organized per year. The main risks are less interest among people in the subject (they could think it was only a private sphere subject) and a not effective communication activity. To mitigate these risks, good communication is needed to make people more concerned about it.

Adaptive Sustainability: The awareness activities can change based on the budget and feedback. The working group is composed of different services of the university, consequently, even if the composition of certain departments changes, there will be continuity to ensure the long-term future of the group's activities. The actions put in place by the working group will change every year according to the needs of the university community.

Generally, the action is considered sustainable because internal services are working on it and the costs are low.

Fourth Key Sustainable Action: Women Empowerment at Work.

GEP area of intervention: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

Objective: To give women more opportunities to develop their careers at university.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is recommended in the GEP, and there is no opposition from the institutional and managerial roles. It is only difficult to do these activities during working hours.

Operational Sustainability: A trust relationship has been established with the external partners responsible for delivering these workshops. One is free and the other is not very expensive and can be paid for by the Gender Equality Mission. If it is not possible, resources (videos, texts...) can be shared on the Gender Equality toolbox. The action is already opened to all the women of the university community.

Cultural Sustainability: A need on the part of many of the women in the university to obtain keys to feel more empowered. Women affirmed gaining confidence after participating in the salary negotiation workshop and in the feminist verbal and physical self-defense workshop. It is already intersectional.

Strategic Sustainability: Capitalization of the free nature of one of the workshops, highlighting the positive feedback from both workshops: the salary negotiation workshop, made by external stakeholders on a voluntary basis, and the self-defense workshop. These workshops help women to

assert themselves, gain confidence and feel empowered and more at ease, especially in an environment where there may be tension. The action can be maintained overtime because it has low costs. The risks are misunderstanding of non-mixity and non-effective communication and can be mitigated with a strong communication with sources on the role of the non-mixity and making people understand that this is not an end, just a means to an end, and that there are many other actions available to men.

Adaptive Sustainability

Adapt workshops based on feedback, consider opening the target audience (making it accessible to men). The action is flexible.

Generally, the action is sustainable because it is needed by people, and it has low costs.

Fifth Key Sustainable Action: Gender, Health and Well-Being.

GEP area of intervention: Measures against GBV including sexual harassment Gender.

Objective: To have a better understanding of physical and mental health issues among women and LGBTQIA+ people at the university.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is supported by institutional and managerial roles, and people from different departments can take part in the working group. GEP recommends at least 3 group meetings per year to define the activities to be worked on in relation to current issues. The working group is flexible (people can take part in meetings that interest them the most, can join the working group at any time, can fully participate and make their suggestions).

Operational Sustainability: The action requires the involvement of several university departments, including the Gender Equality Mission. The tools developed by the working group are free and available for anyone who needs them. The tools developed are meant to be used for awareness-raising stands and posters. The training offered to the group is open to all staff and doctoral students.

Cultural Sustainability: There is a growing interest in the subject among students and staff alike. The action is already intersectional. This action aims to raise awareness on these topics and to give more visibility to thematic.

Strategic Sustainability: This action requires the involvement of the university community and interactive activities. The action can be maintained overtime. The main risk is a lack of interest or

time on the part of group participants. It can be avoided by not having meetings too often, promoting the group to recruit new people and giving them the possibility of attending only the more interesting.

Adaptive Sustainability: Group activities can change according to context and needs. The working group is flexible, and the theme is large. The tools developed are meant to be used for awareness-raising stands and posters. The training proposed to the group is open to all staff and doctoral students.

6.1.5 AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH)

AGH University of Science and Technology (AGH) held the analysis session for GEP's Refinement on 6 June 2025. Participants were four people, 3 females and a male: 3 people of the GEP Team and the Equality Ombudsperson. The analysis session was divided into the following parts:

- 1) Presentation of NEXUS co-designed actions 1-5.
- 2) Evaluation of the running actions: redesign.
- 3) Sustainability workshop: discussion on 5 actions.
- 4) Sustainable actions: report.
- 5) Sub-groups/ blended mode: co-design innovative action.

During the refinement session, AGH reviewed all five co-designed NEXUS actions. Four actions were identified as having strong sustainability potential without major modifications, while one was deemed sustainable with minor adjustments. The sustainability review emphasized the agility of the action designs, enabling responsiveness to evolving social, political, and institutional contexts. The institutional embedding of the actions into existing structures further supports long-term viability. However, as the actions were implemented by a well-established university unit and had been already coherent with their ongoing activities, the sustainability of actions is highly feasible and can be maintained without investment of significant resources.

Considering this discussion, all **five actions were included in the new GEP refinement: “E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality”, “Inclusive communication guidelines”, “Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring Tool”, “Fostering participation in work-related trainings through data collection with a gender+ perspective” and “Information campaign”.**

At the end, the team designed an innovative further action to be implemented after the end of the project: **“Inclusive chat-bot”.**

First Key Sustainable Action: E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality

GEP area of intervention: Gender dimension in research and teaching content.

Objective: To increase awareness and institutional understanding of gender and intersectionality through an interactive, modular e-course.

Organizational Sustainability: The e-course is supported by AGH's unit responsible for internal staff training, and it is a part of a regular training offer. The e-learning system is supported by IT and training departments. All the courses are updated on an annual basis.

Operational Sustainability: The e-course is supported by AGH's unit responsible for internal staff training, and it is a part of a regular training offer. It is available to all AGH's employees, and it is promoted through a regular internal communication channel, such as newsletters. The e-learning system is supported by IT and training departments. All the courses are updated on an annual basis. Instructional designers reviewed the courses and suggested changes based on ongoing evaluation embedded into the training process.

Cultural Sustainability: The action raised awareness among staff responsible for research projects about the issue of intersectionality and gender as the topic has not been present in the university's discourse so far. It also reached beyond the university, to other institutions (such as grant agencies, research centers, and other HE). In future further collaboration with these institutions is planned to refine the course content towards changing research and funding landscape in Poland.

Strategic Sustainability: The action is a part of AGH's Strategy for enhancing internationalization of research and teaching and AGH GEP for 2025-2028. It can be maintained over time although the course will need to go through refinement annually to sustain high quality and relevance to the organizational, legal or other changes. The high risks are the lack of participants and outdated or irrelevant content. These risks can be mitigated with information campaign/dissemination actions and with an annual refinement of the course based on ongoing evaluation by the participants and instructional designers.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is resilient to leadership changes as: it is supported by a learning support unit; it was in line with AGH GEP priorities. The funding for the unit responsible for its delivery is stable and comes from AGH's budget. It is also in line with AGH's Strategy (2023) in terms of internationalization, equality, and equal access. The course is modular and consists of small learning chunks so that additional modules can be added and content can be amended. As it includes some multimedia and video resources that can be developed, re-designed and added to the course structure. Also, the e-learning platform is based on open-source Moodle Solution, so the course can be shared widely. As the course content is available on the OPEN AGH system, it allows participants from other institutions to complete it upon registration and with no costs.

In general, this action is sustainable because it requires low resources to continue sharing the course; it is a stable e-learning environment, and it is embedded into training practices of the institution; it is shared as Open Educational Resource and on Opens Source system; it is easy to update due to its modular structure.

Second Key Sustainable Action: Inclusive Communication Guidelines

GEP area of intervention: Work-Life Balance and Organizational Culture.

Objective: To promote inclusive, respectful language within university communication and create a shared framework for inclusive discourse.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is a bottom-up approach to the implementation of language guidelines. It is non-formal yet advisable to use documents that has gone through an extensive process of consultation all over the university (e.g. With the faculty's deans, students and units responsible for internationalization and research). It is a part of the AGH GEP 2025-28. The guidelines are supported by the GEP Team, The Dean of Faculty of Humanities, Ombudsperson for Equality, and academic teachers.

Operational Sustainability: The action has already been extended to the local PL version of the document as a spin-off action lead by the AGH GEP Team, involving students as major researchers and content creators. The action can be seen as a twofold practice: the content itself and the process of co-design. As a co-design, it is flexible and replicable, and the structure designed can serve well for different institutions as a starting point for further development. As for the content, the learning cycle within the Trio shows the sensitivity of the language and nuances of the local practices that make it very difficult to use the content directly, without further amendments. The action has been already scaled up to the local context (Polish language) as a part of AGH GEP action plan.

Cultural Sustainability: The participatory process of development at the local and international level raised awareness of the sensitivity of the language as a key factor in creating an inclusive environment and shaping institutional practices. The learning process within Trio included discussions about language differences and cultural context of the guidelines. The action was intersectional from the beginning. The Polish document includes more intersectional dimensions, such as age, body, ethnicity.

Strategic Sustainability: As a result of the action, there is a document available on the university's website, and it doesn't require additional resources for maintenance. However, to keep it up to date, the document needs to be regularly reviewed. It can be maintained over time although the guidelines will need to go through refinement annually to sustain high quality and relevance to the organizational, legal or other changes. The main risks are the lack of users and the outdated content. The mitigation of action can be an information campaign/dissemination of actions and an annual refinement of the guidelines based on ongoing evaluation.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action has a highly sustainable content; it has a scalable structure and process. It is already implemented as a variable in Polish language as a AGH GEP project 2025-28. The guidelines are designed as a modular document that can be amended according to the changing needs of the target group as well as to the societal changes (e.g. need to include different areas, extend the range of topics etc.) The action is a bottom-up approach to the implementation of the language guidelines.

In general, this action is sustainable because it has a highly sustainable content, it has a scalable structure and process; it is already implemented as a variable in Polish language as a AGH GEP project.

Third Key Sustainable Action: Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring Tool

GEP area of intervention: none.

Data collection process: the action is aimed at improving data collection.

Objective: To conduct gender+ equality audits using the GEAM tool, adapted to AGH's STEM and male-dominated context.

Organizational Sustainability: Statistical research is supported by a permanent team at AGH, including the Faculty of Humanities and employed sociologists specializing in quantitative research. The implementation of the research using the GEAM tool was supported by institutional and managerial roles, resources, or formal commitments. The survey for employees, students, and doctoral candidates was distributed with a request and cover letter from the Rector of AGH. The research reports were presented to the university authorities.

Operational Sustainability: Statistical research at AGH is supported by a stable, formally established team appointed by the Rector. The team operates with its own dedicated budget and includes experts from the Faculty of Humanities, including sociologists specializing in quantitative research. This institutionalized structure ensures continuity, methodological rigor, and the capacity to conduct large-scale, reliable studies across the university. There is a possibility of replication and flexibility of the action duplicated in different contexts without significant additional costs. In fact, the action has been extended to the entire AGH university, like other departments, target groups, or institutions.

Cultural Sustainability: The use of the GEAM tool for equality research has significantly increased awareness among staff responsible for research projects regarding issues of intersectionality and gender. The topic has also drawn attention from other institutions, including the media and other technical universities, highlighting its growing relevance in the broader academic and social context. The questions can be extended to cover other topics if needed, including issues related to intersectionality. The research increased awareness of unequal treatment at the university across various levels. The results were also discussed in numerous media outlets in Poland. The research results were also included in discussions held by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland.

Strategic Sustainability: Equal treatment is highlighted in AGH's key institutional documents; currently, work is underway on anti-mobbing and anti-discrimination procedures. The research conducted with the GEAM tool has had an impact on the development of these procedures. The action can be maintained over the long term, but it will require updates and the inclusion of important topics that may emerge within the university. The main risks are the reluctance to respond, the lack of trust in the institution, the avoidance of active participation in the research, and insincere answers.

Adaptive Sustainability: The use of the GEAM tool at AGH demonstrates a high level of adaptive sustainability. It is formally supported by the institution initiated with the involvement of the Rector and presented to university authorities. The tool was adapted to AGH's specific context as a male-dominated technical university, showing its flexibility. It can be further developed to include intersectional dimensions and replicated in various contexts without significant costs. The research was implemented across the entire university, confirming its scalability. The GEAM-based study

raised awareness of unequal treatment and had an impact beyond AGH reaching the media and the Ministry of Science and Higher Education. The action is resilient, but only under the condition that the GEP requirement is maintained at universities. If the European Commission lifts this requirement, there is no certainty that such research will continue, due to the political climate in Poland. However, its long-term sustainability depends on the continuation of the GEP requirement in research funding, as the current political climate in Poland makes it difficult to ensure its continuation without such a formal mandate.

In general, this action is sustainable because it is a stable tool for conducting research at AGH, supported by a team of sociologists, including statisticians.

Fourth Key Sustainable Action: Fostering participation in work-related training through data collection with a gender+ perspective

GEP area of intervention: none.

Data collection process: the action is aimed at improving data collection.

Objective: To collect gender-sensitive data on training participation and improve intersectional monitoring.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is sustainable within smaller administrative units, responsible predominantly for developing teaching capacities among the academic faculty. However, since certain training courses are connected to external or one-time funding, comparisons are difficult between units and within time. There is no standard practice of combining data from training led by different units. The gender dimension (along with other data that might lead to intersectional insight) is collected. However, due to privacy concerns (the possibility of connecting data to individuals in cases of more than one dimension) data sharing and publishing in this respect remains an open issue. Furthermore, in the face of lacking an HR central unit, collecting uniform data from different departments remains a challenge.

Operational Sustainability: AGH university is switching to unified electronic documentation. This might be an opportunity to systematize data collection practices. The practice can be adjusted to circumstances; the major challenge remains with a central HR unit and data privacy concerns because metadata standards need to be established. Various data standard initiatives across the

EU and Poland are in action. Possibly hiring or training professional data stewards (which is planned at AGH) would support this action.

Cultural Sustainability: The action doesn't pose major cultural challenges. However, cultural sustainability would be ensured if individuals/units responsible for data collection had clear instructions regarding data handling, considering that data privacy concerns need to be resolved ethically and with compliance with EU and state regulations. This action was aimed at monitoring, so although work-related training has potential and has proven to impact people, practices and policies, the data collection does not translate directly to that impact.

Strategic Sustainability: The main risks are that data may lead to individuals. Therefore, data security standards must be strictly adhered to. Employing professional data stewards and taking responsibility for one central university unit (ideally HR) would strategically enhance sustainability. In fact, the risks can be mitigated through securing data stewards and a central unit responsible for data on work-related training.

Adaptive Sustainability: The resilience of this action would be secured by adopting common standards and having a unit responsible for collecting data about all work-related training.

In general, this action is sustainable because people will continue to participate in training and data on those faculty and staff will be collected. This is an action that is sustainable but with adjustments.

Fifth Key Sustainable Action: Information campaign

GEP area of intervention: Gender balance in leadership and decision making

Objective: To promote equality, anti-discrimination, and diversity via institutional campaigns targeting students and staff.

Organizational Sustainability: The action has been consolidated in the activities of the AGH Communication and Marketing Center, Equality Advocate, Center for Employee Affairs, Rector's Office, AGH Spokesperson, Students' Organizations, AGH GEP Team etc.

Operational Sustainability: The action involves costs (material production, staff, renting equipment, cost of promotion), but the overall structure is replicable as a framework for implementation in different contexts (e.g. other universities and public body institutions). The team implementing this action can also introduce selected elements of the campaign, adapting the promotion to the financial and organizational resources currently available. The structure of the

campaign is replicable and scalable as a framework for implementation in different contexts (e.g. other universities, public body institutions). Further inclusion of different units would support the implementation of the action.

Cultural Sustainability: It is intersectional by design, but it can be extended when needed. Subsequent outreach campaigns can be tailored to current issues of inequality observed within the university and can therefore educate and inform the university community about the most dangerous areas of exclusion at a given point in the implementation of equality policies (e.g. based on social class, ethnicity, etc.). It created a space for joint actions with another Polish universities (Jagiellonian University) and students' organizations as well as other AGH's units. It makes the GEP, and the issues connected with diversity, a visible topic for discussion of various levels (students, faculty, management). It raised awareness on the topic of the organization.

Evolving the action: To professionally promote the activities of the Gender Equality Team and DEI knowledge, a social media specialist will be hired to promote the "Equality at AGH" profile on social media.

Evolving the action: The Equality Open Days at AGH in October 2025 will be organized in an expanded format, as this time the event will include representatives from various polytechnics (technical universities) from all over Poland.

Strategic Sustainability: The action will be maintained as a part of AGH GEP 2025-2028. The main risks are lack of participants; lack of resources due to economic changes; resistance of the community; cyberbullying and criticism of those presented on social media as committed to promoting equality.

These risks can be mitigated as follows:

- Lack of participants: extensive information and dissemination activities, involvement of management and students.
- Lack of resources due to economic changes: sponsoring and external funding options.
- Resistance of the community: education, information.
- Cyberbullying and criticism: Offer support (psychological, etc.) to those involved in promoting equality. Building social support networks and alliances between those supporting equality at universities.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action has its structure that will be adapted annually. After each campaign the community's awareness and needs will change so the amendments to the campaign's plans are necessary to maintain efficiency and engagement of the audience as well as impact of the action. The campaign was designed to include various actors and stakeholders to get involved in the whole process of implementation. It is a part of AGH GEP 2025-2028, so it has sustained funding. In general, this action is sustainable because it is embedded in the equality policies for AGH (GEP 2025-2028). The implementation and maintenance of this action involve people in various positions at AGH (including those with institutional authority), as well as external institutions. This action may be implemented on a part-time basis or developed with additional activities, depending on available organizational resources.

6.1.6 Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (BZN)

Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (BZN) held the analysis session for GEP's refinement on 28 May 2025. Participants were 6 people, 5 females and a male: 3 people of NEXUS Team, a researcher, an internal communication manager and the HR Director. The analysis session was divided into 3 parts:

- 1) A review of all NEXUS pilot actions.
- 2) A discussion about the sustainability of pilot actions and those useful for the GEP's refinement (sustainability report).
- 3) A discussion and analysis of further innovative action to be implemented after the end of the NEXUS Project.

The team was interested in discussing the NEXUS actions in the context of the current institutional GEP which was updated in November 2024. The next update is due in two years' time, in November 2026, and this fact allows for a scope of sustainability and refinement within the frame of even the current GEP. The assessment was conducted on all 5 NEXUS pilot actions, but only two actions were considered sustainable and eligible for GEP refinement.

The discussion started with the analysis of the pilot actions and their outcomes, followed by a discussion on the sustainability of pilot actions, in terms of a GEP's refinement and ended with a discussion on the further and innovative action to implement after the end of the project. At the end of the discussion, however, the team was skeptical about the overall impact and the take up of the current actions, citing various issues, such as low interest in staff, low sense of relevance of the GEP among employees and low sense of trust in that the actions are targeting relevant gaps or issues existing within the institution. Each of these issues needs to be addressed to make the follow-up process more sustainable than targeting the NEXUS action portfolio.

Considering this discussion, **two actions were included in the new GEP refinement** out of the five that had been planned and implemented with NEXUS: **“Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring (GEAM) Tool”** and **“Inclusive communication guidelines”**.

At the end, the team designed an innovative further action to be implemented after the end of the project: **“Guidance and training supporting inclusive and nonviolent communication in a professional context”**.

First Key Sustainable Action: Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring (GEAM) Tool

GEP area of intervention: Gender balance in leadership and decision making.

Objective:

- Gather data from the GEAM Survey.
- Map the situation regarding gender equality in BZN.
- Create an updated database for each Institution in the trio.
- Be able to make comparisons, keep track of changes, improvements, or pitfalls.

Organizational Sustainability: The current institutional GEP lists this action as one to be repeated every four years. As stated in section C1, available at this [link](#), the organization is accustomed to and prepared to run horizontal surveys from time to time. The management generally values feedback from such surveys.

Operational Sustainability: After the initial investment in resources (i.e. translation of the template and learning the use of the e-tool), significant further investment is not needed. The action is replicable; the tool is adaptable and flexible, even if it is managed by stakeholders outside the NEXUS project. Questions may be modified according to demand but keeping in mind the comparability perspective (comparison with earlier survey results and measurement of change with time). The GEAM tool as such is very flexible to be run in different environments and contexts.

Cultural Sustainability: The survey already includes many dimensions; therefore, extensions are not planned. On the contrary, focusing on fewer areas could result in a higher response rate and more motivation to answer. The potential impact is directly linked to the institutional coverage measured by the number of responses. Impact needs time to be visible, and therefore we see the most potential impact to surface upon repeating the action and compare/monitor trends over time.

Strategic Sustainability: The action requires commitment from relatively few people, therefore the GEP team responsible can ensure sustainability over time without larger scale involvement of staff. However, a related risk is that internal communication needs to be motivated enough to guarantee good participation in the survey itself. Commitment is key to using the results of the survey. The main risks are the low motivation of the staff to fill in the survey and the resulting low response rate and the approval of the leadership, which can be mitigated by convincing them that the results are useful.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is technically adaptable and flexible in case of needs to change. The leadership will always have the ultimate say in judging whether they want to continue this action, and changes in leadership may result in changing priorities that might affect the replication of the action with respect to what is envisaged now. Now, following the first full run of the action, technical knowledge as well as lessons learnt about the success of the action will both contribute to adaptation towards desired results.

In general, the action is sustainable because it is easily replicable, and it gives a full view of the institution's strengths, weaknesses, and gaps only in a historic comparison.

Second Key Sustainable Action: Inclusive communication guidelines

GEP area of intervention: Measures against gender-based violence and harassment.

Objective:

- Design guidelines to make communication within and outside the university fairer and more inclusive.
- Enhance competences: knowledge, skills, and attitudes.
- Provide the community with a practical guidance on communication patterns in English for inclusive language.
- Set standards for internal and external communication.
- Share lessons learned and support mutual learning among the Trio.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is more like in a neutral position now. The Guidelines are a new initiative for the organization without significant preliminaries or history.

Operational Sustainability: The action is replicable and flexible; in fact, we are convinced it may yield higher impact by tailoring it to the changing external circumstances and by offering it in the Hungarian language as well. Resources are needed for this, but needs are not excessive, and professional knowledge is already in place provided by the NEXUS team

Cultural Sustainability: The action is flexible insofar as the content of the guidelines is open to updates, changes, and adaptations. Proper document control is important in this case, but no other major risks are present. It can be extended along intersectionality dimensions; however, this is seen as beneficial as far as it stays relevant for the diversity level of the organization. Since the action is being rolled out just now, the effect of impact is not yet visible.

Strategic Sustainability: Due to its flexibility, it is important to define clearly the scope and objective of the updated guidelines. Risks include sub-optimal reach and use, or the content becoming obsolete or nonrelevant. Careful monitoring of the policy framework and other external factors is needed to address these risks. As stated above, this document will need regular updates to stay relevant. The availability of internal resources and institutional commitment both play a role here. The risk is that this kind of guide has never been produced or used by the institution. A possible way of mitigation is to adapt the content to the institutional needs (intersectional map) if the original content does not work. Another mitigation measure is to show why the guide is useful, which is a lengthy process and will depend on the personal choices and preferences of its users (i.e. some will like it, and others will not).

Adaptive Sustainability: More than adaptable, this action highly depends on adaptation, i.e. the proper follow-up of evolving internal and external circumstances. This requires appropriate human resources as well as commitment from leadership, and the guide is useful in contributing to this. It is adaptable since it is a synthetic document built on a few sources selected based on relevance. Thanks to the high volume of available resources identified during the preparatory work, the content can easily be changed and updated. However, this will need staff time.

In general, this action is sustainable because with the wealth of resources available in this field, it is easy to tailor and adapt existing content to produce our own update, in case the risks above are successfully mitigated.

6.1.7 University of Nis (UN)

University of Nis (UN) held the analysis session for GEP's Refinement on 16 May 2025. Participants were four people, 3 females and a male: 2 people of NEXUS Team and two professors. The analysis session was divided into 3 parts:

- 1) A review of all NEXUS pilot actions:
- 2) A discussion about the sustainability of pilot actions and those useful for the GEP's refinement (sustainability report).
- 3) A discussion and analysis of further innovative action to be implemented after the end of the NEXUS Project.

The University of Nis conducted an assessment on all 5 NEXUS pilot actions that have been considered all sustainable, and they will be considered in the new GEP refinement.

The session took place in a good atmosphere and lasted for about two hours. The discussion started with the analysis of the pilot actions and their outcomes, followed by a discussion on the sustainability of pilot actions, in terms of a GEP's refinement and ended with a discussion on the further and innovative action to implement after the end of the project. Considering this discussion, all five NEXUS pilot actions will be included in the new GEP refinement. At the end, the team designed an innovative further action to be implemented after the end of the project: "Improved quality of studies for the disabled".

First Key Sustainable Action: Influence of biases in decision-making

GEP area of intervention: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

Objective: Tackling bias in recruitment.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is supported by institutional and managerial roles, and most decision makers supported and attended the training.

Operational Sustainability: The training is replicable and can be repeated after the end of the NEXUS project. It is adaptable; it can be applied to a broader audience and can be transformed into guidelines concerning the need for additional training.

Cultural Sustainability: The action fosters internal dialogue on bias and inclusion. It is extensible and has been addressed with an intersectional approach. The impact is positive; it can evolve, because biases have been addressed with an intersectional approach.

Strategic Sustainability: The action is aligned with an inclusive recruitment strategy; it has structural integrity and can be maintained over time. However, partners figure out different risks, firstly that most of the decision makers could pass the training once they participated in the first one, or it could be a lack of interest in future training. These risks could be mitigated with guidelines designed for new staff and increasing interest in the old ones.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is adaptable, and updates will be provided. No significant costs are necessary for future changes. Gather material design guidelines after end of NEXUS.

Second Key Sustainable Action: Parenting Group

GEP area of intervention: Work-Life Balance and Organizational Culture.

Objective: Identify and engage 2 community builders.

Organizational Sustainability: The action has no formal commitment, but there is approval for using the workspace for meetings. Community builders are members of the teaching staff of the UN, who will continue to organize events.

Operational Sustainability: There are no obstacles for replicability each year, but it is flexible for changes based on feedback from parents. Established vibe communication group channel for exchange of information and setting meetings of interested parents.

Cultural Sustainability: The action is extensible, and it can include intersectional problems if they occur at parenting meetings. Engaged parents to help improve work life balance issues based on exchange of experience. The action has a good impact because the people who were directly involved have a positive attitude and are willing to participate further with 1 to 2 meetings per year.

Strategic Sustainability: The action has structural integrity and can be maintained over time because community builders should maintain it. Main risks are the motivation of parents: motivation of parenting community and community builders can decrease over time. Monitoring and shaping activities in line with the expressed community interest should help mitigate this risk. It has been approved to occupy the UN workspace for parenting meetings.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is adaptable: there are community builders who will organize, monitor and tailor future events during the meetings. The action is adaptable to future changes, and funding is not necessary.

Third Key Sustainable Action: Gender and Intersectional dimension in research

GEP area of intervention: Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content.

Objective: A gender approach in the research field.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is supported by institutional and managerial roles that promote publication on institutional websites. Maintained through availability of guides on website.

Operational Sustainability: The action is replicable since it requires no costs, and the guide is online and free to use. No maintenance can be duplicated in different contexts.

Cultural Sustainability: The action is extensible, and the intersectionality is embedded in the guide. Encourage innovative approaches, including GE+ in research practices. The young researchers were informed, and the use of guides was presented. It can evolve by feedback from users and adaptation to future needs and research areas.

Strategic Sustainability: The action has structural integrity, and the action can be maintained over time because the guidelines can be redesigned based on evolution of research or change of policy. The main risk is that researchers choose not to use the guidelines, but now there is no space for mitigation. It is aligned with European Commission priorities and national Science Fund priorities.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is adaptable to changes, and the guide can be adjusted in line with change of EU or national policy. The action is adaptable also to future changes and doesn't require funds. Guidelines will be updated with policy changes and user feedback

Fourth Key Sustainable Action: Informing employees and students about the existence of the Regulation on Prevention and Protection from Sexual Harassment at FMEUNI (RonPPfromSH)

GEP area of intervention: Measures against GBV included sexual harassment.

Objective: Wellbeing in the workplace and study environment.

Organizational Sustainability: Management in general provides full support for this action. It is anchored in institutional training programs.

Operational Sustainability: The action is replicable without additional costs; it can be scaled up, and the model designed on the website can be replicated. Use of existing UN resources for training.

Cultural Sustainability: The action is extensible and can have an intersectional approach. Regarding the impact, the students were informed when a new year starts, and staff were informed on the procedures and website page. Based on feedback, it can evolve over time. Supports a safe and respectful work environment.

Strategic Sustainability: The action has structural integrity; with the person in charge elected periodically by the members of the teaching staff. The action can be maintained over time thanks to training trainers. The initiative has led to improved prevention measures, a higher level of awareness, and better access to information. Additionally, the process of filing complaints via the website is simple and accessible. However, the main risk is that participants may comply only formally, without this translating into real changes in attitudes or behaviors regarding the topic. There is also a potential lack of interest in future training sessions.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is adaptable and updated for legal changes, and it is adaptable to future changes. Resilience is due to a person in charge that is periodically elected and to a trainer on the topic. The UN will work on gathering data and monitoring, for continuous evaluation and improvements.

Fifth Key Sustainable Action: Better environment for Roma students at the faculty

GEP area of intervention: Work-Life Balance and Organizational Culture.

Objective: Increased number of Roma students at the faculty.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is supported by institutional roles: the Dean signed the contract with NGO and approved the measures designed. Maintained through institutional support for promotional activities and availability of enrolment data on the website.

Operational Sustainability: The action is replicable without additional costs; it can be scaled to other faculties in Serbia, that can adopt similar actions. The maintenance of website data is scheduled annually; collaboration with NGOs is preferred.

Cultural Sustainability: The action is extensible, and the intersectionality is applied to Roma students. The action started adopting tailored measures for motivating Roma students to study and

based on feedback these measures can evolve. The team for promotion encouraged to further improve the pathways for promotion of University of Nis to potential Roma students.

Strategic Sustainability: The action has structural integrity, and it can be maintained over time without significant costs. The main risk is the lack of motivation for Mechanical Engineering. If there is a significant increase in the number of Roma students, budget for dormitory costs of scholarship may be a limiting factor. Special programs can be designed, and NGOs may help with funding. The action is aligned with national regulation for higher education of Roma students.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is adaptable for changes based on feedback from promotional activities, NGOs, and success rates. It is also adaptable to future changes, and it is resilient without significant funding. Monitoring and evaluation of promotional activities for continuous improvement are required.

6.1.8 Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT)

Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT) held the analysis session for GEP's Refinement on 21 May 2025. Participants were four people, 3 females and a male: 2 people of NEXUS Team, one person of the GEP Team and HR Manager. The analysis session was divided into 3 parts:

- 1) A review of all NEXUS pilot actions:
- 2) A discussion about the sustainability of pilot actions and those useful for the GEP's refinement (sustainability report).
- 3) A discussion and analysis of further innovative actions to be implemented after the end of the NEXUS Project.

The session took place in a positive and dynamic atmosphere and lasted for about two hours.

Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia conducted an assessment of all 5 NEXUS pilot actions. Three key actions under the NEXUS framework have been assessed as sustainable, and they will be considered in the new GEP refinement.

The discussion started with the main results that emerged from the redesign and the formative evaluation, to analyze the state of implementation of the action, its future sustainability in cultural and organizational terms, and eventually reached an assessment of what can or cannot be included in the GEP. Considering this discussion, **three actions were included in the new GEP refinement** out of the five that had been planned and implemented with NEXUS: **“Bias in Recruitment and Career Progression”**; **“Recognizing and Addressing Harassment in the Workplace”** and **“Gender & Intersectional Dimensions in Research Guidelines”**.

At the end, the team designed an innovative further action to be implemented after the end of the project: **“Guidelines on inclusive language”**.

First Key Sustainable Action: Bias in Recruitment and Career Progression

GEP area of intervention: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

Objective: Strengthening awareness and management of bias in evaluation processes.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is supported by top management, and it will be embedded in internal guidelines and in the evaluation processes. To address the risk of low usage, especially within a small internal audience, a brief survey will be conducted to gather feedback on potential improvements and suggested changes. In the long term, it would be valuable to analyze

whether the tool has had a measurable impact on the diversity of the IIT community. There is no big risk to the continuation of the action.

Operational Sustainability: The action is scalable and repeatable; it has a broader audience, and it can be repeated in different units/departments. The action requests a low-cost periodic review through HR focus groups.

Cultural Sustainability: The action is extensible because bias has been addressed with an intersectional approach and fosters internal dialogue on bias and inclusion. It is amplified thanks to a broader audience, which is a positive aspect. It could have an intersectoral impact if proposed to those who are part of the external committees in the selections for the tenure track office, potentially becoming the best practice at IIT in the long term.

Strategic Sustainability: The action is aligned with an inclusive recruitment strategy. It is a sustainable tool with no bigger risks and can be maintained over time.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action doesn't require specific investments from those who use it. Guidelines can evolve based on feedback and emerging needs.

Second Key Sustainable Action: Recognizing and Addressing Harassment in the Workplace

GEP area of intervention: Measures against gender-based violence and harassment.

Objective: Develop internal capacity to prevent and manage workplace harassment.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is supported by the top management that has a formal agreement on it. This action will be anchored in institutional training programs.

Operational Sustainability: The action is adaptable to future changes because it will become part of mandatory training, and regulatory updates related to the topics are included. The training will use the existing Health and Safety structures and platforms.

Cultural Sustainability: The action can support a safe and respectful work environment. It has an intersectional approach. A broader audience and a different setting, focusing on harassment and workplace safety as well as work-related risks.

Strategic Sustainability: The action reinforces IIT's risk prevention and HR policies, and it is linked to a mandatory requirement (structural funds). The risk is that participants will join the training only for formal compliance with the absence of a real change on the topic. This risk can be mitigated by

the alternance between training moments (receptive moments) and in-person workshops or practical case studies (active moments).

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is adaptable, and a regulatory update is included. In addition to that, the content will evolve via trainer focus groups and internal feedback. The action is adaptable to future changes because, being part of mandatory training, it will be resilient.

Third Key Sustainable Action: Gender & Intersectional Dimensions in Research Guidelines

GEP area of intervention: Gender dimension in research and teaching content.

Objective: Equip researchers to integrate gender+ in research proposals.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is supported by the top management and other organizational units involved in the topics, like the Project Office, Communication Directorate, and others. This action will be maintained through the institutional project support framework.

Operational Sustainability: The action is flexible and replicable because no specific or dedicated costs are identified. The action and its output are scalable. There is low-effort maintenance. No specific or dedicated cost is identified; the action is also highly replicable.

Cultural Sustainability: The action encourages reflexivity and responsible research practices and can impact research and the EU Framework. The intersectionality is already part of the guidelines 'content. Project office could consider including it as a topic within the research sustainability area

Strategic Sustainability: The action has structural integrity and can be maintained over time with updates. The main risk is that the audience may not use the guidelines. The action is aligned with European Commission priorities.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action will be updated considering the European programs and policies in coordination with Project Office. Guidelines will be also updated with policy changes and user feedback.

6.1.9 Koç University (KU)

Koç University held an analysis session on 29 May 2025. Participants were 10 people, all females, including faculty members, administrative staff, researchers, sustainability staff. The session successfully reviewed five major NEXUS actions implemented at Koç University. Participants offered rich feedback on the sustainability and scalability of each action, discussing factors such as language accessibility, institutional visibility, interdepartmental cooperation, cultural sensitivity, and long-term engagement strategies.

Key themes identified include:

- The necessity of localized and repeated delivery for training content (especially in Turkish).
- Strong need for community engagement, regular workshops, and visible campaigns.
- The importance of integrating student clubs and administrative staff into the sustainability model.
- Recommendations for aligning mentoring and development programs with real-world needs and ensuring they address intersectional challenges.
- Multiple innovative action proposals were made, including gender equality ambassadors, menstrual leave, and campaigns targeting male engagement.

The session concluded with a discussion on the next steps and potential avenues for sustaining the actions through future collaboration. All five NEXUS actions were reviewed and assessed for their sustainability, to ensure a comprehensive and inclusive evaluation, but only 4 actions were considered sustainable.

Koç University conducted an assessment on all 5 NEXUS pilot actions. Four key actions under the NEXUS framework have been assessed as sustainable and are now considered for integration into the upcoming Gender Equality Plan. The pilot action “**Seminar Series on Anti-Feminist Algorithms and AI Bias**” was recognized as the thematic focus for the 2024/2025 period and discussed in relation to selecting a new theme for 2025/2026, therefore not listed in the sustainability report.

Finally, the “**Gender Equality Ambassadors Program**” was selected as the innovative and inclusive action to be implemented following the conclusion of the NEXUS Project.

First Key Sustainable Action: Gender-Based Violence Online Module

GEP area of intervention: Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment.

Objective: To raise awareness and build capacity around recognizing and preventing gender-based violence (GBV), with a focus on Bystander Intervention.

Organizational Sustainability: It aligns with Koç University's gender equality commitments and is integrated into mandatory onboarding. It is supported by IT, HR, Student Affairs, and the Gender Equality Office.

Operational Sustainability: The action is highly replicable and scalable. Visual content makes it easy to adapt across universities or even non-academic settings. Strong digital infrastructure and institutional support help. Language and staffing may be limiting factors. In fact, the action might be translated into Turkish; it requires a periodic rollout, and coordination between departments.

Cultural Sustainability: The action matches community concerns and cultural needs of the university community. It can include dorm-specific content, multiple languages, and topics like sexual orientation-based violence or ethnic discrimination, with wider collaboration. It sparked discussions on bystander roles, safe spaces, and the need for better visual communication.

Strategic Sustainability: The action aligns with long-term goals of GEP and aligns with broader anti-GBV efforts on campus. It sparked discussions on bystander roles, safe spaces, and the need for better visual communication. With continued support and regular updates, it can become a lasting part of university orientation. It meets a clear need, fits university values, and can be embedded in existing systems for long-term use. The main risks are low visibility and outdated content. These can be mitigated by translating and contextualizing the content in Turkish, integrating it into campus visuals (e.g., dorms, hospital screens), establishing feedback mechanisms, and engaging student groups.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is overseen by the Gender Equality Office, a small team reporting directly to the vice president, allowing for flexible and efficient adaptations. The action may evolve based on feedback, suggesting strong support if adapted for different contexts. It can be integrated into routine processes like onboarding. Formal policies and shared ownership would further strengthen resilience. The content can be updated and localized based on community feedback. Language adjustments may require more effort.

Generally, the action is sustainable because it meets a clear need, fits university values, and can be embedded in existing systems for long-term use.

Second Key Sustainable Action: Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression: Needs Analysis

GEP area of intervention: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

Objective: To identify gaps and opportunities in mentoring support structures for doctoral students, researchers, and faculty members.

Organizational Sustainability: The action has a strong institutional interest and support.

Operational Sustainability: The action requires repetition (every 2-3 years) to monitor changing needs. The survey and needs analysis were specific to Koç University community but since the results align with general needs and trends discussed in academia, they may as well be duplicated. It can be tailored to various disciplines and career levels.

Cultural Sustainability: The action resonates with current academic concerns and evolving research culture. The action identified core areas of mentoring needs and exposed a major structural gap. It has already shifted the conversation from informal support to intentional mentoring. The action has intersectional dimensions.

Strategic Sustainability: The action is aligned with satisfaction and equity objectives. With proper coordination and an action plan, the structure can evolve into a lasting university mentoring program, and the survey may be repeated every 2-3 years to monitor progress. There are no risks.

Adaptive Sustainability: The results of the needs analysis provide a flexible foundation to adjust mentoring content and structure based on changing needs. The action can be tailored to various disciplines and career levels. It is evidence-based, meets clearly expressed institutional needs, and can be conducted with minimal resources. Resilience would be enhanced through shared ownership across multiple units and a formalized feedback loop.

Generally, this action is sustainable because it is evidence-based, meets clearly expressed institutional needs, and can be conducted with minimal resources.

Third Key Sustainable Action: Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success

GEP area of intervention: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

Objective: To design and pilot an inclusive mentoring framework that reflects the diverse needs identified in Action 2.

Organizational Sustainability: The mentorship program actively involves key support offices (Vice Presidency for Academic Affairs, Dean of Students, Alumni Office, Gender Equality Office, and Graduate School administrations) and is integrated into their existing structures and work plans.

Operational Sustainability: Clear processes, defined roles, and ongoing feedback ensure effective day-to-day management and continuous improvement of the mentorship program. It requires coordination with internal and industry stakeholders. The model adapts to all disciplines and career stages. Its thematic focus and flexible formats, like group or reverse mentoring, make it highly replicable with minimal costs beyond commitment. Alumni involvement and industry partnerships support scaling.

Cultural Sustainability: The action is aligned with community needs and can evolve academic trends, fostering stronger connections between academia and industry. The mentoring model can be extended to support underrepresented groups, parents in academia, and those with non-traditional career paths. Thematic or life-stage mentoring—such as navigating gatekeepers or balancing doctoral motherhood—enables a broad, inclusive approach. The action is already intersectional.

Strategic Sustainability: the action can be institutionalized through collaboration with career development and academic support units. It supports a long-term cultural shift in mentoring aligned with leadership vision for deeper integration of industry within academic research. The main risks are low motivation and lack of mentor follow-up, over-reliance on volunteer enthusiasm. Mitigation includes starting with a small pilot, collecting feedback to build commitment, and highlighting program impact and visibility.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is flexible across diverse career paths, embracing a transdisciplinary approach. Its resilience would be enhanced by formal institutional backing—such as integration into onboarding and/or academic development plans. It can also incorporate new formats such as peer, reverse, or group mentoring, allowing flexibility to evolve with changing needs. Generally, action is sustainable because it meets institutional and broader academic needs, is adaptable, low-cost to pilot, and supports diversity and equity in career progression.

Fourth Key Sustainable Action: Skills Development Program

GEP area of intervention: Gender balance in leadership and decision making.

Objective: To equip researchers and doctoral students with key transversal and soft skills.

Organizational Sustainability: The action is aligned with leadership's broader researcher development strategy and supported by shared training resources. The program is piloted with science communication training and has received high engagement from doctoral students. There is visible support from all academic units, institutional leadership, and individual faculty members. The action meets a clear, ongoing need for development of transversal skills, especially among early-career researchers, and its flexibility and low-cost implementation make it a strong candidate for institutionalization.

Operational Sustainability: The action is scalable and repeatable; it fits within multiple offices' work plans and strategic priorities. Once materials and facilitators are available, implementation costs are low. Thanks to the pilot action, skills development can be maintained covering other themes reported in the survey. Limiting factors include availability of facilitators and time allocation for training. Institutional backing, a training calendar, and support from units like Career Development or Teaching & Learning Offices can enable scale-up.

Cultural Sustainability: The action fosters engagement and peer learning; strong community buy-in reflected in survey results and pilot participation. There's an interest in expanding these topics to include personal growth themes (e.g., social media use for science communication, dealing with failure, curiosity in research). The program already touches on areas like confidence-building. It can include further themes such as impostor syndrome or navigating gendered academic environments. The action has already intersectional dimensions. In the long term, this program can cultivate a more supportive and self-aware academic culture.

Strategic Sustainability: Deriving from pilot action, skills development can be maintained covering other themes reported in the survey. Supports broaden university goals in employability and research excellence. The action advances university goals in employability, research excellence, and development of key skills like communication, networking, and work-life balance. The main risks are low prioritization compared to "hard skills," lack of incentives for trainers (faculty) The risks can be mitigated with a formal integration into graduate or early career training programs, rotation of

workshop topics to maintain relevance, and showcasing participant feedback to secure ongoing support.

Adaptive Sustainability: The action is flexible across departments; it addresses diverse skill needs and serves as a for future programs. If anchored to central training units (e.g., Graduate School, Career Development), the program can survive changes in leadership or policy. Periodic needs assessments and modular design would help maintain its relevance and resilience. Training topics and formats are highly adaptable. Survey and Feedback mechanisms from previous sessions can inform updates, and delivery methods (e.g., online, interactive workshops) can be changed to match evolving needs.

Generally, action is sustainable because it meets a clear, ongoing need for transversal skills development, especially among early-career researchers. Its flexibility and low-cost implementation model make it a strong candidate for institutionalization.

6.2 Template (Annex A and B), Sustainability Reports, Summary table for further actions

Technological University of Dublin (TU Dublin), Ireland

GEP refinement session: a) [TUD_GEP Refinement](#) and b) [TUD_GEP Refinement_2](#)

Frederick University (FredU), Cyprus

GEP refinement session: [FredU_GEP Refinement](#)

Sofia University (UNISOFIA), Bulgaria

GEP refinement session: [SU_GEP Refinement.docx](#)

University of Le Mans (UM), France

GEP refinement session: [UM_GEP Refinement](#)

University of Science and Technology (AGH), Poland

GEP refinement session: [AGH_GEP Refinement](#)

Bay Zoltán Nonprofit Ltd. for Applied Research (BZN), Hungary

GEP refinement session: [BZN_GEP Refinement](#)

University of Nis (UN), Serbia

GEP refinement session: [UN_GEP Refinement](#)

Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT), Italy

GEP refinement session: [IIT_GEP Refinement](#)

Koç University (KU), Turkey

GEP refinement session: [KU_GEP Refinement](#)